

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D4.1: Report on Youth Motivation Strategies

WP4 – Engagement and Motivation Strategies for youth
participation

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			literature – more emphasis on Sense of Community	
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1 Executive summary

The goal of this deliverable is to present a strategy for young people engagement with environmental issues via the STEP platform. The deliverable begins with a presentation of the key project’s objective to which this deliverable answers. It then goes on providing a definition of how the term “strategy” is used in this work, in particular focusing on the elements of a strategy as composed of a diagnosis of the situation and on the definition of a guiding policy for action. The deliverable then offers a diagnosis of the situation based an analysis of materials. For the diagnosis of the situation the deliverable considers three sets of material: relevant literature on youth motivation to engage with environmental issues; a re-analysis of data gathered via qualitative interviews (conducted for Task 2.2 of STEP) and the data gathered as outcome of a cultural probe specifically conducted as part of the activities of Task 4.1. In particular, the deliverable discusses key concepts related with young people engagement with the environment identifying the notion of action over that of attitude as a possible basis for building engagement for STEP. This concept is taken further in the deliverable via the re-analysis of interviews and with the analysis of the data coming from the cultural probe. The deliverable then concludes with a number of recommendations for action to be implemented during the pilot operations of STEP.

2 Introduction

The overall objective of the project STEP is to develop and pilot test a cloud e-Participation SaaS platform, (available as a mobile application and through a web platform), whose goal is to engage Young European Citizens (YECs) and Public Authorities in decision making about environmental strategies, policies, plans, programmes, laws, and projects. Since the project aims at the validation of the STEP platform/service in view of its wider deployment and use, the involvement of users in a pilot operation under realistic conditions is essential for its success. The pilot operation will be conducted under the auspices of the Work Package 5 of the project. To support the activities of the pilot operations, the project seeks to develop engagement and motivation strategies for youth participation and the investigation of these strategies is the focus of the Work Package 4 of which this **Deliverable 4.1 Report on Youth Motivation Strategies** is part. Specifically, this deliverable – together with other deliverables related to WP4 activities – contributes to answering one of the key sub-objectives of the STEP project:

Objective 3: To develop **engagement and motivation strategies** for increasing youth participation in environmental decision making

The research work described in this deliverable offers a study on strategies to encourage youth involvement in environmental decision making by the mediation of the STEP platform – which is based on empirical evidence in the form of literature and data gathered specifically for the STEP project. One of the core aspects of STEP is to provide a set of tools, innovative concepts, creative ideas, and strategies for **youth participation** that leverages social media to help environmental policy makers engage young people. The work conducted for this deliverable in particular connects with the goal of investigating **strategies for youth participation** in order to foster young people engagement in environmental decision making.

As the goal of the deliverable 4.1 is to discuss strategies for youth participation, the work will initially provide a definition and some perspective about how the term strategy is used in this work, in particular focusing on the elements of a strategy as composed of a diagnosis of the situation and on the definition of a guiding policy for action. This comes from the work on strategy by Rumelt (2011). The deliverable then offers a diagnosis of the situation for STEP based on an analysis of materials. For this, the deliverable considers three sets of material. Firstly the deliverable discusses key literature concepts related with young people engagement and action toward the environment identifying the notion of action over that of engagement as an attitude as a key element for building engagement via STEP. Secondly, this concept is then taken further in the deliverable via the **re-analysis of interviews conducted for T2.2** and with the analysis of the data coming from a **cultural probe conducted specifically for the T4.1**. The deliverable then concludes with a number of **recommendations for action** to be implemented during the pilot operations of STEP, which are grounded in the diagnosis of the situation.

3 A note on the notion of Strategy

While it is not the scope of this deliverable to delve in current debates about the concept of strategy it is important to offer some perspective on the way this term is used in this work. This is because the goal of this work is investigating **strategies for youth participation** in order to foster engagement in environmental decision making. The term strategy comes from the Greek (*stratēgia*) and it could be seen as the art of drawing a plan of action and its conduction. In this deliverable we adopt the perspective of the book *Good Strategy/Bad Strategy* by Rumelt (2011), as this offers a solid and rather innovative perspective on strategy. In particular, in this perspective, a strategy can be reduced to a kernel of specific and well defined elements for building a targeted plan for action.

In the book, Rumelt (2011, p. 2) discusses that the fundamental aspect in strategic planning is “*discovering the critical factors in a situation and designing a way of coordinating and focusing actions to deal with those factors*”. A strategy therefore is not the definition of grandiose goals but rather an honest analysis of the situation faced by an organisation or project and the devising of a plan for action to tackle identified obstacles. Inevitably knowledge of the situation in which a strategy needs to be inserted will be fragmented and never complete and the means available for action could also be limited due to constraining factors, such as time or material resources. However, in this perspective the key aspect of a good strategy is not necessarily the forward plan for action but first and foremost an attempt to **inquiry in the situation** faced by a project or organisation. A good strategy, in Rumelt’s (2011, p. 4) perspective is in the first place something that “*honestly acknowledges the challenges being faced and provides an approach to overcoming them*”, it is about **defining how a project can take steps to move forward out of a definition of a complex situation and limited set of resources**. Rumelt’s ideas will be used in this deliverable to organise thinking around a strategy for the engagement of young people with environmental decision making via the STEP platform. The key elements for

a good strategy – defined by Rumelt (2011) as the kernel (p. 77) are a diagnosis of the situation, a guiding policy and a set of actions. These are briefly defined as follows:

1. **A diagnosis of the situation** which aims at defining the challenges faced by a project or organisation. This can be seen a critical understanding of what is the situation and what are the critical factors in place.
2. **A guiding policy** is the attempt of drawing an approach to deal with the challenges identified in the diagnosis. It is a sort of perspective for action which can be used to tackle obstacles and issues that have been identified in the diagnosis of the situation. The guiding policy should aim not only at defining a set of actions but also ideally aiming at ruling out actions that potentially will not yield expected results or will not help in overcoming obstacles.
3. **A set of actions** which are necessary for the actual implementation of the guiding policy. This also means that these actions and the resources employed should be coordinated toward achieving the policy.

In the perspective discussed here, there are additional elements that can help a project or organization develop a strategy. Some of these elements are relevant for the discussion of this deliverable and the work to be conducted for STEP and in particular:

Strategy as design: according to Rumelt (2011, p. 124) a successful strategy requires to work on the anticipation of people's action. This is essentially a matter of seeing the strategy as a sort of design action, in a situation in which the strategy more than a set of decisions is the process of crafting a plan for action. For STEP this is particularly interesting as the platform is also in fact the outcome of a design process and this ties with the discussion presented in D2.2, where design requirements have been presented as the process of finding out what to do before creating it. Therefore, a strategy requires some anticipatory work aimed at understanding actors future actions and anticipate possible issues.

Strategy as experiment: in this perspective the strategy as defined via a diagnosis of the situation needs to be seen as a hypothesis guiding action. It is a sort of informed plan about the situation and a plan which is set to define what may or may not work. This also means that the hypothesis needs to be tested in practice and actions are to be seen as an experiment trying to validate or not the hypothesis.

Critical thinking: forging a strategy requires critical thinking. The strategy is hence less the outcome of the application of a pre-determined framework or grid of analysis and it is more about the capacity to take a position on an issue. Such position could be developed with a proper diagnosis of the situation and with decisions on how to act in such situation.

Developing independent judgment. This is a further important aspect and essentially is the idea that the creation of the strategy should not be about following what everyone else is doing. Judgment about the strategy should be independent and based on existing evidence, data, analysis and available resources and opportunities.

A final clarification is needed before continuing the discussion. It is not the goal of this deliverable to transform a strategy into action and therefore this work does not cover the point 3 of the strategy kernel discussed above (SET of ACTIONS). As D4.1. aims at tracing strategic directions for youth involvement and engagement with environmental decision making via the STEP platform, this deliverable focuses on the **diagnosis** and **guiding policy**, whereas the **actions** will be followed up in the WP5 piloting activities. The strategy developed in this deliverable comprises therefore the following:

1. A **Diagnosis** based on existing material and data – (see next section for a description of material used in this deliverable and the research and data collection conducted).
2. A **guiding policy** in the form of a series of recommendations for action to be tested as hypothesis during the piloting phase. These recommendations are outcome of critical thinking and independent judgment in relation to the diagnosis of the situation.

Figure 1 – Youth Motivation Strategy and its distribution across WPs

3.1 Material Used for the Diagnosis of the Situation

This deliverable comprises three sets of material which were used to conduct a diagnosis of the situation and reflect on courses of action for STEP and the engagement of young people with environmental decision making:

1. A review of relevant literature on the subject of youth motivation to engage with environmental issues at a general level.
2. A reanalysis of data gathered via qualitative interviews conducted for STEP (conducted for Task 2.2).
3. Outcomes of a cultural probe specifically conducted as part of the activities of Task4.1

The reason for conducting a **literature review** stems from a precise choice: base a diagnosis of the situation for STEP also on some of the key issues and research debates related with youth engagement with the environment. While the review does not pretend to be exhaustive, it however serves some relevant strategic and scientific scopes. In the first place, a review will act as a scientific “umbrella” for the research specifically conducted for STEP. Indeed the review will not only allow us to connect the research results of STEP to the wider scientific and policy debates related with young people engagement with the environment. The review will also offer the basis for a more solid interpretation of the STEP research original data (collected with interviews and a digital cultural probe) in the light of the goal to design a strategy for action. The review also serves a further scope: identify relevant distinctions and concerns of current research when it comes to youth engagement with the environment. The research conducted for STEP is qualitative and design oriented and while it goes in-depth in the analysis it does so for selected case studies and small number of individuals. Most of the existing research around the engagement of Young people with the environment is quantitative and based on scales. This research may offer explanation to surface trends, but offers limited material that can be used for inspirational/design purposes, whereas in STEP due to the designed nature of the project (i.e. the creation of an online/mobile platform) design oriented research is favoured. Ultimately in the perspective adopted here, **strategy** is not about fitting data into an explanatory-deductive framework but is about finding inspirational directions for the design of strategic actions. The literature offers concepts which can help STEP shape its strategy, but qualitative data offers empirical evidences upon which to base action.

As part of the activities for the definition of user needs (Task 2.2), partner Abertay has conducted a number of **qualitative interviews** with Young European Citizens (YECs¹). The interview did contain specific questions related with YECs engagement with environmental issues. These questions were aimed at gathering material to be used for modelling personas and scenarios, with a focus on including aspects of engagement/disengagement with environmental issues in personas and scenario narratives. However the use of this data should not be limited to the goals of D2.2 and it deserves further scrutiny and interpretation for building the STEP strategy around young people engagement with the environment. Therefore this deliverable contains a reanalysis of this data with the identification of some key themes developed via the Grounded Theory approach which has already been presented in D2.2. These themes will in particular be linked with current issues in existing literature and with the outcomes of the literature review.

The main research instrument used for the data collection for Task 4.1 has been a **digital cultural probe**. Cultural probes are a technique which is traditionally based on a “physical” kit (usually containing a diary, sticky notes/postcards, a camera and other recording tools) that allows the users/stakeholder to record relevant aspect of their life. The Probe provides a way of gathering information about people and their ordinary life activities. Cultural probes can also be constructed as **digital probes**, leveraging existing web based technologies and this was the choice for STEP (a full description of the STEP probe is provided in section 6 of this deliverable). In particular during the writing of the original proposal for the STEP project it was decided by partners to adopt the probe technique in order to conduct research in the diverse geographical and cultural contexts related with STEP (primarily in the pilot countries but also across other areas of Europe), thus reflecting the need to capture the perspectives of geographically dispersed users. The STEP Digital Cultural Probe has been constructed explicitly focusing on daily activities that youth conduct with particular attention to their routine involvement in environmental issues (e.g. recycling at home, travelling to school/work) but also with their explicit reflection on decision making in environmental issues.

4 Literature on Young People and Environmental Engagement

The literature analysis conducted for this deliverable has considered material coming from different perspectives and considering different angles. Conceptually, several distinctions can be made to help navigate the existing body of knowledge. The key distinction that will be considered in the following pages is that between the **attitude** in engaging with environmental issues (including decision making) and that of environmental **action**. What we propose and discuss in the next pages is that while the notion of attitude can help explain engagement with the environment – including young people engagement – it is limited in purpose for the goals of STEP. This is because an attitude is something which is developed over a long period of time and is highly dependent from socio-demographic factors, which are largely outside the control of a project like STEP. The notion of environmental action may seem more difficult to approach in the first place because it requires actors to make an effort to actively participate, however we believe it offers solid concepts upon which some elements of a strategy for STEP can be developed.

¹ The abbreviation YEC is used in this deliverable when referring specifically to Young People residing in Europe and in particular in relation to young people who have been involved in the research for STEP. Some of the literature considered in this report considered Young People on a more general perspective (e.g. not living in Europe), where this is the case or the issue can relate to Young People in general then the abbreviation YP (Young Person) is used.

4.1 Environmental Attitudes of Young People

According to Eagly and Chaiken, (1993) an attitude can be defined as a sort of "*psychological tendency that is expressed by evaluating a particular entity with some degree of favor or disfavor*". An attitude is a predisposition – which can be therefore positive or negative – toward specific issues such as values, people or ideas. Attitudes are generally developed over time and are dependent upon a number of contextual factors. A positive or negative attitude can also be developed toward specific issues and the engagement with them.

In the study of **attitudes** of young people toward environmental issues a common distinction is often made between **demographics factors** and **social factors** influencing said attitudes and subsequent behavior and engagement (Dietz et al. 1998). Demographic factors are structural elements of society and they include aspects such as age, social class, residence (urban/rural), political orientation and sex/gender. In this case, the assumption is that variations in demographic factors have a causal influence toward environmental engagement as an attitude. For instance one of the key hypothesis in literature is the so called **Age-Hypothesis** (Van Liere and Dunlap 1980), namely that young people tend to be more concerned than older people with the environment. Assumptions are for example made that young people have more stakes in the future (Riemer et al. 2014) and that younger generations have been more exposed to environmental information and the need for civic and personal action in favour of the environment than the older generation. This hypothesis is however far from transparent and, for instance, data from a very recent Eurobarometer survey (European Commission, 2014) about EU citizens engagement with the environment shows that young people (15-24) have far less engagement than older people in relation to several environmental issues such as the importance of protecting the environment but also having an interest in playing a role in environmental change.

Another demographic factor which has received wider attention is the **gender hypothesis** with research showing that females are generally more concerned than men about the environment (e.g., Zelezny, Chua, and Aldrich, 2000; Hunter et al., 2004). Elements that have been used as an explanation relate for instance the women's role in parenting, with females taking on roles as caregivers and nurturers (Blocker and Eckberg, 1989; Hamilton, 1985). Some contradictory research however, shows little difference between males and females with regards to environmental concerns (e.g., Tindall et al., 2003). Hunter et al., (2004) provided evidence for cross-national gender differences in private environmental behaviors such as recycling, buying organic produce, or driving less, but found little support for gender variation in public environmental behaviors such as supporting an environmental organization, signing petitions, or taking part in demonstrations. Their research also suggests that there are gender differences in "public" relative to "private" environmentally-oriented behaviors, with women more actively engaged in household-oriented (private) pro-environment behaviors (e.g., recycling), and men more actively engaged in community/society-oriented (public) pro-environment behaviors (e.g. protests) (Blocker and Eckberg, 1997 and 1989; Davidson and Freudenburg, 1996).

Material conditions of life - the **social-class hypothesis** (Van Liere and Dunlap 1980) - have also been linked with different levels of engagement and the idea that environmental concern is positively associated with factors such as education, income, and occupational prestige. An obvious assumption here is that the less people are concerned with immediate needs, the more they can dedicate attention to other aspects of life. The research by Hunter et al. (2004) mentioned above, also looked at cross-cultural variation in engagement, and found an association between GNI (gross national income) and variation in private behaviors, with women engaging in more private behaviors relative to men, particularly in wealthier national contexts. Although again this hypothesis is far from transparent and there are research contributions that showed that people with limited material resources are far more affected by environmental problems than those who live in better socio-economic conditions and hence also have a significant level of engagement and this also includes young people (Wilson and Snell, 2010).

Another two hypotheses complete this overview. The first one is the **residence hypothesis** (Van Liere and Dunlap, 1980), namely that environmental concern is correlated with where a person lives. For instance people living in urban locations appear to be more concerned and engaged with environmental issues than those living in rural locations. de Pauw and Petegem (2010) have shown that attitudes are also shaped by the presence or absence of relevant natural resources in the areas where people live. We can also look at this from a national perspective across Europe, the Eurobarometer 416 (European Commission, 2015) shows significant differences among EU Countries in relation to different issues. For example “At individual country level, people in Hungary (68%), Finland and Portugal (both 66%) are the most worried about air pollution, while those in Ireland and Estonia (both 47%), and Latvia and Germany (both 49%), are the least worried.” (p. 13). Or again as another example “When it comes to water pollution (the second most common concern at European level), Finland (67%), Greece (64%), Sweden (64%) and Latvia (61%) have the highest proportions of people who say they are worried about this, while Poland (37%), the United Kingdom (39%) and Malta (40%) have the lowest.” (p.14). The last hypothesis is the **political hypothesis** (Van Liere and Dunlap, 1980) namely that there is a relation between voting for progressive or conservative parties and the concern with the environment, with the former being more concerned than the latter. It seems obvious to assume that young people voting for ‘environmental’ parties such as the Green Party will be more engaged with environmental issues, but it is likely for this to also be linked to supporting more left wing parties which are generally more supportive of interventionist government policies for protecting the environment.

In the reflections conducted around the notion of attitude, some factors clearly emerge from a strategic perspective. The goal of STEP is to develop and pilot test a cloud e-Participation SaaS platform, (available as a mobile application and through a web platform), whose goal is to engage Young European Citizens and Public Authorities in decision making about environmental strategies, policies, plans, programmes, laws, and projects. When it comes to direct a strategy in relation to attitudes it is clear that STEP has no power to influence the demographic elements, for instance increasing the material conditions of participants so that they could develop a more favourable attitude towards engagement with environmental issues. On the other hand, STEP cannot directly target activities to certain categories of young people as this would create discrimination, for instance focusing more attention to people living in urban rather than rural areas or more on female than male participants. In the STEP strategy the diagnosis of the situation is that demographic elements are a given factor – a constant – and this clearly constitutes a limit that needs to be taken into account as part of the strategy.

Approaches that consider **social factors** as relevant for explaining environmental attitude and engagement consider aspects such as: socialization, social norms (normative theories), learning and communication processes and the relations between values and attitudes. **Socialisation** in particular has been widely considered in literature as a key factor driving positive attitudes and engagement and ultimately leading to pro-environmental behavior. Socialisation is a process – widely discussed in sociological research - whereby members of a social group learn and interiorize norms, values and customs of the group (Parsons and Bales, 1956). When it comes to environmental attitudes several authors have pointed to the relevance of socialization processes taking place with a particular focus on socialization within the **family**, the formal **education system**, via influence of the **media** and among **peers** (de Vrede et al., 2014). The family in particular is often seen in literature as the social group where pro-environmental socialization of young people often takes place, with parents being the primary actors in the process of socialization of young people. In this case we can talk about the *family/norm socialization*. Grønhøj and Thøgersen (2009) also note that “*Not only values, but also specific behaviours and attitudes towards behaving in a specific way are learned in the family, through observational learning and direct influence*”. This further points to the assumption that norm interiorisation via socialisation include also observation of parents’ behaviour and attitude toward the environment. Interestingly, some authors have also argued about the opportunity for a reverse socialization in which YP behavior and attitude may influence older generations (Ballantyne et al. 2006) toward having a positive

attitude to the environment. Formal education and specific education programmes have also been positively linked with positive environmental attitude and action (see later for action). Environmental Education Initiatives or EEIs (UNESCO, 1978) offers a basis for this. Studies have found a positive correlation, for instance between energy literacy and energy consumption (Zografakis et al. 2008). In general, the literature shows there is a strong belief that engagement with the environment can be directly linked with scientific and civic education (e.g. Chawla, 1999). It is also hypothesised that higher levels of education are likely to make individuals more comfortable with information presented to them by decision makers meaning that higher levels of education are likely to be positively related to willingness to act (Xiao and McCright, 2007). Likewise the media and various communication programmes also offer a basis for pro-environmental socialization (see Östman, 2014) and the internet and new media also have a role in this type of socialisation (European Commission, 2014).

The research community has developed a number of research instruments in order to measure and/or explain attitude toward the environment, for instance in relation to norms or values. Theories include the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991), norm focus theory (Cialdini et al., 1991) or the value-belief-norm model (Stern et al. 1999). These theories and models are also often accompanied by instruments to measure engagement and these vary in terms of their scope and measures. Probably the most influential is the **New Environmental Paradigm** (NEP) scale (Dunlap and Van Liere, 1978) which is often seen as a fundamental step in the measurement of people's environmental attitudes. *In this view, nature is seen as a limited resource, delicately balanced and subject to deleterious human interference.* The NEP “clashes” with what is defined as the Dominant Social Paradigm of endless progress and abundance which however contributes to environmental degradation. The scale therefore seeks to measure a sort of shift/change in perspective in the relationships that humans have with the environment. The NEP has primarily been used to measure environmental attitude in adults (Dunlap et al. 2000; Dunlap, 2008), however we have specific adaptations of this for Young people and children (e.g. Taskin, 2009; Manoli et al. 2007).

In building a strategic approach for STEP, the same considerations discussed before for demographic aspects, apply to social factors. STEP does not have the ability to affect social factors, and the goals of the project do not include intervening in aspects such as the socialization of young people, educational programs or how the media socializes YP. Not to mention that these are processes that take place over several years (e.g. from when people are children right up until well into adulthood). Social elements related with norms and values are also a given element of the situation for STEP, upon which it is difficult, if not impossible to intervene directly. It could be likely that STEP can better “perform” with the engagement of YP who have been exposed to environmental education or relevant socialization processes, but again acting on these elements or discriminating among participants on the basis of their exposure to specific social dynamics is not feasible, nor recommendable.

Ultimately, from this preliminary review of literature related to the engagement of people – and in particular young people – with the environment as an attitude it emerges that it is unlikely for STEP to impact on existing macro-social and structural dynamics (e.g. demographics) or localized social facts (e.g. socialization in the family or educational programs). It may be possible to leverage these dynamics when they are in place (e.g. if in a pilot the general attitude of people toward the environment is already positive), provided however that these do not create any discrimination.

4.2 Environmental Action

More than focusing on engagement as a general individual attitude which is supported by underlying demographics or social factors, a better strategic option for STEP could be to focus on the idea of

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environmental action. In social sciences the notion of **action** is a key concept and can be preliminary defined as a situation in which an agent orients his/her doing taking in account others. Social action requires also intentionality and is directed toward specific goals (e.g. Weber, 1978). **Environmental action** has been defined by Emmons (1997) *“as an action that involves deliberate decisions, planning, implementation, and reflection by an individual or group intended to achieve a specific environmental outcome”*.

When talking about environmental action a first important aspect needs to be acknowledged: it is widely accepted in literature and policy debates that there is the gap between a positive environmental attitude and the actual action for the environment. The first (a positive attitude) does not necessarily translate into the second (an action). This aspect has been reported in scientific publications but also in policy reports of the like of the Eurobarometers (see for example Special EUROBAROMETER 295 – European Commission, 2007). Literature has also pointed to the existence of a decline in public participation and social capital (Putnam, 2001) at a very general level (not just toward the environment), an aspect which according to research also impinges on participation regarding environmental action. Nonetheless the existence of this gap should not be seen as a limitation in the perspective of STEP, as ultimately the project seeks to engage YEC in shaping policy and participate in decision making. This is, after all, a concrete action. What is relevant for STEP is therefore not necessarily the attitude but primarily the action of young people taking part in decision making processes supported by an e-participation platform. This will require YEC action in the form of participation in the platform, discussions etc. Therefore engagement with environmental action appears more relevant for STEP’s success also in the light of the considerations discussed in the previous section that engagement as an attitude needs to be taken as given element of the situation for STEP. In brief, the notion of action could be a better starting point around which to shape a strategy.

In this regard a second distinction to be made here is that between **behavior** and **action**. While there could be overlaps between these two notions, the former is something which is done but which does not necessarily require immediate reflection or intention. While behavior may be habitual, actions require intentional decision making (de Vreede et al. 2014) and intention – the actor is intentionally doing something. Put it more simply, while behavior relates with current practices and their possible change, an action is seen as something that requires decision making and is oriented toward tackling root causes. Changes in behavior can be triggered by positive or negative reinforcements but this does not necessarily mean that the actor is either aware of these root-causes or that he/she is intentionally seeking to do something for the environment. For instance a person may decide to abandon going to work with a car and use public transport instead. While this would help the environment with a reduction of emissions this could be due for example, to negative reinforcement introduced by public authorities such as an increased fee for parking the car near work which makes public transport a more attractive option. In this case while the change in behavior may help the environment, and the decision to increase parking fee made by the authority could also be aiming to reduce car transits and emissions, this is not done by the driver with intent to tackle specific causes of environmental concerns but it is due to a negative reinforcement. In contrast, if a person decides to use public transport over the car to go to work and this decision is being taken with an explicit (moral) goal of helping the environment, this may be conceptualized as an action: there is a specific actor’s intention aimed at the root-cause and the action is conducted with a clear environmental goal in mind (Jensen and Schnack, 1997). Summarising:

The **first element** of an environmental action is that one decides to do something (alone or with other people), whether it is a change in behavior or influencing general condition of life

The **second element** of action is that the action must be targeted towards solutions to the environmental problem at stake.

One step further is the notion of **action competence** (Jensen and Schnack, 1997). We believe that this notion may offer a better basis for building a strategy for STEP, even if its origins are in environmental education. This

is because the notion points to aspects which can be developed, designed and nurtured within an e-participation platform like STEP. To understand this we need to introduce this concept. Action competence is a notion that has been developed in the area of environmental education, in particular in Nordic countries such as Denmark (Breiting and Morgensen, 1999). The concept is in itself is a critique to educational approaches that focus more on triggering changes of behavior than on stimulating intentions to tackle causes of environmental issues. It is also a notion which criticizes individualistic approaches – where the focus of action is only that of an individual – and emphasizes the participatory and collective need of actions. Action competence has been defined as follows: *“an individual’s capacity of critically selecting and conducting possible actions that may solve societal problems through democratic mechanisms”* (Odabaşı, et al., 2011). This reasons with a definition of environmental action provided by Schusler et al. (2009) *“Adapting this definition, we suggest environmental action is a process of co-creating environmental and social change that builds individuals’ capabilities for further participation contributing to personal and community transformation”* As such these definitions both point to key strategic aspects for STEP: the selection of an action which could be conducted via participatory and democratic mechanisms, in which collectives of participating individuals join forces for a social and environmental transformation.

In an effort to summarise key elements discussed in diverse literature contributions on environmental action and action competence (e.g. Percy-Smith and Burns, 2013; de Vreede et al. 2014; Jensen and Schnack, 1997; Riemer et al. 2014), it is possible to identify a number of relevant dimensions of action, all of which could be included in strategic actions for STEP:

Youth ownership and empowerment: this includes aspects of the like of the desire to *“make a difference (16) Perception of the ability of youth to lead themselves (15) Confidence in leadership skills (14). Perception of youth as positive change agents and role models”* (de Vreede et al. 2014). Or, as Percy-Smith and Burns (2013) note: *“Central to promoting the increasing role of young people as agents of change in communities is the provision of spaces which are not always controlled by adults or defined by the adult agenda but which also provide opportunities for young people to take action in response to issues they feel passionate about”*.

Youth Leadership: (Percy-Smith and Burns, 2013; de Vreede et al., 2014): while not every YP will necessarily display leadership, this is an aspect which in literature has been considered important. In environmental action projects involving young people, leading figures could emerge and lead others to achieve shared environmental goals and it is important to offer opportunities for leadership to emerge. Those Young People who have high social influence are likely to engage others young people.

Participation: Inside conceptualization of environmental action a further distinction could be made between approaches focused only on the individual and approaches more oriented toward an activity in a situation in which is acknowledged also the participatory and collective need of actions. Authors have pointed about the importance of peer participation and the opportunity for young people to *“share ideas, tips, and even tease each other in a lighthearted way about their choices.* (de Vreede et al. 2014).

Stakes in the future: as discussed before there is some agreement that a positive attitude toward the environment is correlated with the idea that YP have more stakes in the future of the environment than current adult generations. It has also been noted that a key motivating factor for environmental action is the need to protect the environment for future generations (Ballantyne, 1995). Having stakes in the future is an important element motivating action toward the environment, especially for Young People. According to de Vreede et al. 2014 (p. 37) *“Committed and action-competent young people provide a valuable force, which can influence change as they have a great investment in future quality of life and can approach problems with a fresh, optimistic view”*.

Experiential: action toward the environment for young people does not seem much related with abstract principles but rather with direct and own experience. This does not mean it is not related with global issues, but that the issues that mean most to them are the ones that have had a direct impact on their lives. Significant early influences such as experiences outdoors and positive role models are important in developing an interest in the Environment (Bögeholz, 2006; Chawla, 1998). Experiential learning alternates between action and reflection, Young People make sense of the world by building on the theories they learn through action and reflection. The relationship between the antecedents of action and the actions themselves are cyclical and mutually reinforcing (de Vreede et al. 2014).

What have we learned from this literature review that would help support the activities for STEP? In the first place the literature sees YP’s engagement with the environment as something dependent upon a number of variable demographic and social factors. These include aspects such as age, residence or material possession as well as socialization and education. It is clear that the situation is that these factors are outside the control of STEP. STEP can intervene in offering YECs the opportunity to take an active role in shaping decisions. The participation with STEP does require YECs to go beyond positive attitudes and this would be related with the idea that STEP offers an opportunity for action, tapping into existing motivation for engagement. Ultimately more than on the engagement in itself, STEP would offer a means for action, an action which could be supported, avoiding individualism and focusing on collective **action**.

5 STEP Interviews and Engagement

The literature analysis conducted for this deliverable has considered material coming from different perspectives but has mainly focused attention on the difference between Environmental Engagement as an attitude and as an action. The literature analysis helped with identifying some critical aspects of the situation for supporting young people in their engagement with environmental issues via a web/mobile platform like STEP. In this section of the deliverable we offer a re-analysis of the interviews with YECs that were conducted for the activities of the Task 2.2. While these interviews were conducted with the specific goal of obtaining qualitative material for modelling personas and scenarios, these interviews also generated a wealth of data, including relevant material on young people’s engagement with the environment also in relation to e-participation and the STEP project. There is therefore wider scope for reconsidering and re-analysing some of this data for building the STEP strategy of engagement and in particular for the diagnosis of the situation. The material from the literature in fact constitutes something of a broader scale/context whereas these interviews were conducted directly for STEP with a clear focus on the pilot countries and municipalities². In particular three questions asked in the interviews were directly related with YECs engagement and motivations:

² These interviews were conducted during the period June-August 2015

We would love to know how important is for you the protection of the natural environment? What things do you do in your personal life for this?

In your opinion, how important is for other people of your age the issue of environmental protection?

How do you imagine the future of the environment? And how do you see yourself contributing to building this future?

The first two questions addressed engagement and motivation with environmental issues and resulted in discussions about what issues were most important for Young People and how concerned they and their peers were about these issues. The third question promoted discussion on the future of the environment; this provided a valuable insight into Young people's perception about how their action could impact global factors such as Climate Change.

5.1 Themes Emerging from Re-Analysis of Interviews

As discussed in D2.2, material from interviews has been analysed using an approach informed by Grounded Theory (Charmaz, 2014). Grounded theory is an inductive perspective that aims at creating concepts and theories starting from the data. Building blocks of Grounded Theory are codes or themes that are developed by the researcher: it is essentially the process of assigning to portions of interviews a theme that captures some ideas contained in the portion under analysis. In a good Grounded Theory themes will repeat themselves i.e. they can be applied to multiple portions of several interviews. In this way concepts can emerge inductively out of the data. Since the process used for the analysis has been described at length in the previous deliverable D2.2 we will not repeat the description here.

To understand youth motivation for participating in environmental issues and decision making we have identified several themes emerging from the interviews, we will examine these positive and negative issues contributing to motivation and engagement below. These themes will further support our diagnosis of the situation for the STEP strategy for engaging young people on environmental issues.

Key "Positive Engagement" themes emerged in the analysis:

- Relevance to the lives of Young People; Direct Impact
- Greater Awareness of Environmental Projects
- Empowerment and Sense of Community
- Seeing Positive Change
- Stakes in the Future

Key "Negative Engagement" themes:

- Environment not main Priority
- Pessimism for long-term Global Future
- Lack of Trust

5.1.1 Positive Engagement Themes

Young people are keen to be taken into consideration more and have their voices heard about the future of the environment. Listening to young people via Participatory approaches when designing and implementing environmental policies improves the understanding of the young person's perspective and can also attract their attention about issues and gain their commitment. It is important to design interventions that are within people's limits of tolerance, and to build support for such interventions (Gardner & Stern, 2002). Increasing young people's involvement and engagement in environmental policy making is the main aim of the STEP

project and we are keen to consider all the aspects that could have an impact on improving this positive engagement. Below we discuss the themes emerging from our interview data that we feel make a positive contribution to their engagement.

5.1.1.1 *Relevance to Young People's Lives*

The findings of the interview data suggest that for young people to be engaged with environmental issues they need to appreciate the effect that it has on their lives in a more direct way. Most young people have other, more immediate priorities, such as getting through exams, finding a job, finding a partner, working, socializing etc. With all the other local and global issues in the news, then sometimes environmental issues can seem quite abstract and removed from their immediate concern, and the policies relating to the issue are complex and out of reach. The young people we interviewed also pointed out that the discussion should be on **topics that they are interested in** and relevant to their lives. This further confirms the need to work around issues that are of direct relevance for young people lives over general global environmental issues or abstract concepts. Visible evidence seems to have more of an impact than future predictions from scientists. With so many other priorities in their lives, an appreciation of how a complex process such as Climate Change can directly impact their everyday life will mean it is of greater concern to them rather than just being an abstract idea. Young people suggested that **an appreciation of a direct effect is important to increasing engagement** with the environment as evidenced by the following quotes:

"It's difficult to say to people 'look climate change is happening', with mining for example, you can see the mountain cut in half. People need to see concrete evidence to believe. People have to try and frame the knowledge with their existing beliefs and see what impact it will have on their own life". UK YEC

"To get people interested you have to make things relative to their lives, for example if you don't do something about an environmental issue then it will have an impact on your life."
UK YEC

This confers with some existing research (e.g. Matthews and Limb, 2003; White, Bruce and Ritchie, 2000) which show the importance of a local focus and on demonstrating the relevance of politics to young people. It seems to be the case that issues such as Climate Change are more abstract to them, and that individuals feel helpless to stem the production of greenhouse gases. Young people from smaller countries may feel that even National level policies to reduce these gases will be of little consequence on the overall global scale. Having the focus on **Local Issues** where people's **actions could have a direct impact** on the outcome was the preferred choice of the young people we interviewed.

5.1.1.2 *Awareness of What's Happening Elsewhere / Idea Sharing*

Young European Citizens were interested in **having high quality, trustworthy information** about initiatives and projects happening in other countries and felt that they could learn a lot from these and that perhaps similar projects may help their own country. Young People also expressed the desire to **learn from others** and to develop positive relationships with other European citizens in sharing ideas. They mentioned that in some cases they can learn from the solutions of the EU, without having encountered the problems first and effectively learn from other people's mistakes.

"I think it is important to know what is going on, not just in your own country but on a global level." Greek YP
"Comparing cities and activities happening elsewhere - I think it is

interesting to know what is happening in other countries, especially Turkey and Greece. People have different ideas, it's good to gather them in one app/website as you can share ideas and learn other things. " Spanish YEC

Young people were however keen to point out that online debate and discussion should not entirely replace real world interaction on environmental issues and decision making, but suggest that the STEP platform could be a valuable tool in supporting these activities by **widening access and participation** to those not able to physically attend a meeting and in providing extra information to all interested parties.

5.1.1.3 Empowerment & Sense of Community

Feeling part of a community is important to Young People and those young people who participate in civic activities are likely to be much more engaged in general. Similarly, young people who are more connected to other people are likely to be more engaged in civic activities, for example, Zhang et al. (2010) found that the use of social network sites was significantly associated with increased civic participation in the United States, highlighting an interesting benefit of social media. For political issues social media interaction and specifically social media campaigning also makes it significantly more likely that young people will talk about politics and an upcoming election to people around them. A recent survey showed that 70% of the young people exposed to a social media campaign talked to at least one of their close friends about the election, compared to only 58% of the young people exposed to the traditional campaign (Youth Participation in Democratic Life EACEA 2010/03) .

"It is very important for Young People to be involved in local & civic activity or movements, it will enrich their lives a lot and give them new tools. The reality is different though, most young people do not participate. We need to increase the awareness of what is happening within the city" Spanish YEC

"How am I supposed to save the environment on my own? Good to get a more collective mindset - a good idea to use the approach of the group action. Collaboration between the public & private sectors too." UK YEC

Having a sense of community and getting people to work toward shared goals was often mentioned in the interviews (and also confirmed by the posts made in the Cultural Probe discussed in section 6).

The concept of collaborative action and of working together was important to the young people interviewed, they expressed the need for increased discussion between themselves and the older generation(s) as well as greater collaboration between public and private sectors to work toward better environmental outcomes.

The idea of a sense of community is seen as important, it is also one of the key factors in developing successful e-Participation. The concept of a 'Sense of Community' (SOC) is described by McMillan & Chavis (1986) as 'a feeling that members matter to one another and to the group, and have faith that members needs will be met through their commitment to be together'. SOC theory has been shown to be important in many online and offline communities (O'Brien et al 2016) including virtual learning environments (Palloff & Pratt, 1999), e-commerce (Koh et al, 2003) and social media communities (Zhang, 2010; Scheepers et al. 2014).

McMillan and Chavis (1986) developed a set of scales to measure sense of community. They hold that a sense of community has four elements.

- Membership indicates that people experience feelings of belonging to their community.
- Influence implies that people feel they can make a difference in their community.

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- Needs fulfillment suggests that members of a community believe that the resources available in their community will meet their needs.
- Emotional connection is the belief that community members have and will share history, time, places, and experiences.

This sense of community can be nurtured in motivating user participation in virtual communities, researchers (eg Zhao et al. 2011) have tried to understand what attracts people to virtual communities and what impacts their willingness to share or get information from these communities. It seems that a 'sense of belonging' is important (Roberts, 1998), this can be defined as 'the experience of personal involvement in a system or environment so that persons feel themselves to be an integral part of that system or environment' (Hagerty et al. 1992). There is a lot of commercial interest in this area as companies such as Amazon are keen to retain and nurture their customer base. Social Capital Theory describes the resources rooted in relationships (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998), and although intangible, social capital is considered an important resource in a social system and has been shown to be related to knowledge transfer (Chow & Chan, 2008). Zhao et al. (2012) found that three factors relate to the dimensions of social capital in virtual communities (VC); **familiarity** with members in the VC, perceived **similarity** with other members and **trust** in other members. These factors are all positively related to the sense of belonging (and SOC) which affects intentions to share knowledge and mediates the relationships between social capital factors and a member's intention to participate.

Recent efforts to address declining civic and political engagement by offering citizens a way to get involved via e-Participation have been widespread, with evolution through early dissemination of information, then more interactive communication and eServices with e-Participation evolving beyond top-down government led processes to include citizen-led e-Participation through various formats including social media. O'Brien et al, (2016) introduces the concept of Sense of Community to the e-Participation research field, highlighting the important mediating effects of SOC to critical Public Value outcomes, investigating how a SOC can be created in e-Participation and asks what are the Public Value components in e-Participation. The paper proposes that developing a SOC contributes positively to Public Value (PV) outcomes, by increasing:

- Trust
- Participation in decision making
- Transparency
- Legitimacy
- Political Efficacy
- Effectiveness

These factors, in turn increase Satisfaction of the e-Participation system and also people's intention to use it.

Off-line activities/meetings can complement the relatively low social presence inherent in virtual communities (Koh et al. 2003) and may strengthen the relationship building process of a virtual community. STEP intends to utilise this effect by planning real-world events with local communities (see section 4 Pilot Plans in D 5.1).

5.1.1.4 Seeing Positive Change Increases Motivation and Engagement

The benefits of having achievable goals and seeing positive change was discussed by both the policy makers we interviewed and the young people themselves. Demonstrating the impact of any involvement is very important to the Young people we interviewed. This confers with research showing that 89% of young people want proof that getting involved makes a difference (Office for Public Management, 2004).

“Young People are motivated when they see that the things they are doing have a consequence, a result. If they see that changes happen then they will be interested and motivated. “ Spanish YEC

However, not seeing any action after they have become engaged in the decision making process and offered their opinion would very likely have a negative impact.

“I think perhaps that STEP or similar platforms, if we can ask for the opinions & suggestions of YP and citizens in general, they are taking into account that in 4 years that if they don't see their suggestions having any impact then they won't get re-elected. You can ask us but you have to be seen to be taking us seriously and we need to see action, otherwise there will be a huge disappointment. “ Spanish YEC

The policy makers we spoke to confirmed the point that young people really need feel that they are being listened to and also to see that the actions they take do make a difference:

“Young People need to see something change – a result. They think everything has to be resolved. They think they have to be useful. One successful event was a river clean up – they could see a collection of tires along the river. This was successful as they saw the result. “ Italian Policy Maker

This would suggest that the platform should make an effort to provide as much feedback as possible about the effect that any actions made by the YECs have. Following up any consultations with results for example, or providing photographs and reports about projects that young people contribute to would increase their engagement and the likelihood that they will participate again in the future.

5.1.1.5 Young People Having High Stakes in the Future

Young people have higher concerns and responsibilities in relation to the environment than older people. Environmental risks and hazards will disproportionately affect young people, as they are the ones who will have to live for an extended period with the environment bequeathed to them by earlier generations. They will have to live longer with the consequences of current environmental decisions than will their elders. Not only they, but their own children and future generations will also be affected by decisions made and the extent to which concerns about the depletion of resources, climate change, pollution and the loss of biodiversity are addressed. This should in itself be a motivating factor for engagement and action; Young people will be increasingly likely to engage in new forms of action and activism to provide effective responses to the challenges facing them.

“Young People are very important, these are the people that could change their ideas and thus change the world. YP should be listened to – they are the ones who will come up with innovative ideas for the future.” Italian YEC

“Young People could create relationships with each other and share ideas on environmental issues. These are important in saving our future. Our environment is our future, we have to believe in the possibility to live in a better world”. Italian YEC

It seems that uncertainty about the longer term future is increased by the feeling that not everyone is concerned or prepared to change. The feeling that policies are not addressing the longer-term issues did not help younger people feel optimistic about the future for the environment.

5.1.2 Negative Engagement themes

Not all the themes emerging from the data were positive of course and in this section we consider the negative issues regarding the engagement of young people with the environment. The fact that young people are a very heterogeneous group and for the majority the environment is not at the top of their list of immediate priorities should be a major consideration for the STEP project. Pessimism and how to mitigate this and promote optimism is another, whilst the issue of Trust (especially with regards to politicians and policy makers) is an hurdle to overcome in order to engage many YEC's in the policy making process.

5.1.2.1 Environment is not always the Priority for Young People

The idea that the environment is not always the key priority for young people was heard frequently, even amongst the more environmentally aware young people we interviewed. This was especially true in areas where there is high youth unemployment. Even the young mayor of Spain who we interviewed said that Politics was not always a priority and it would have been difficult to get him and his friends involved in Policy Issues a few years ago.

“Young people often have other things on their mind. Probably 10 years ago it would have been difficult to get me and my friends involved in these things (politics).” Young Policy Maker Spain

“Many people my age are not caring enough about the environment. Some people do care and are really worried about the environment, but not enough people”. Greek YEC

Many of the young people interviewed said that they were concerned about the environment, but were often too busy to become more involved with environmental action and/or discussions about environmental policies. The perception of environmental engagement being difficult was expressed, decreasing the barrier for young people to become engaged by making it easier for them should be one of the key strategies for STEP.

“I am quite concerned, but I haven't been involved to any extent with any environmental actions/organisations. Mainly I am very busy and this is the reason. I think if I had more time or it was a bit easier then I would give it a try (online platform).” Greek YEC living in UK

The biggest challenge for STEP will be to try and engage young people who are not currently interested in the environment. Even when young people are interested, then getting them to find the motivation to participate will not be an easy task. For this reason the platform developed needs to be very well designed and easy to use and not too time consuming for them to participate. We need to be aware of these negative issues mentioned here and try and mitigate against them to promote a feeling of positive change and how their actions can have a real impact towards short-term goals, but also emphasizing how multiple small change across a large geographical area can add up to a large and sustained positive impact on the longer term future of the global environment.

5.1.2.2 Pessimism over Long-term Future of the Environment

Almost universally the consensus was pessimistic for the long-term future of Global issues, however there was greater optimism about improvements in their local environment and how much could be achieved if people

were willing to act collectively to make changes. Our interview data shows that young people were generally pessimistic about global, long-term issues such as Climate Change. Some YECs wondered what difference a small European country could make in reducing CO₂ emissions when much bigger countries such as India and China were still emitting vast amounts of greenhouse gases. They felt that positive environmental actions could make a difference at a local level, however they felt much more powerless to address global issues such as Climate Change. The research literature seems to back up these findings; although many young people think climate change is an important societal issue, studies indicate that feelings of hopelessness, pessimism and helplessness are common (Ojala, 2012a; Connell et al. 1999; Eckersley 1999; Flear, 2002; Hicks and Bord, 2001). A study by Hurrelmann, and Quenzel (2010) showed that although young people are optimistic about their own future, two-thirds think climate change threatens human existence. This also seems to be the case from our interview data, they felt **more optimistic over their local environment** and the opportunities for action at a local level however than they did for the global future of the environment. The quotes below help to highlight this point:

“Not so good if we continue doing what we do now. I am not optimistic, If people don’t change their habits it will be bad.” Spanish YEC

“I am quite pessimistic about the future of the environment. I believe people should be more concerned about it.” Greek YEC

How does pessimism relate to motivation? Researchers have argued that hope is important for environmental engagement (e.g. Lueck, 2007; Ojala, 2012a; Ojala, 2012b). Health psychology researchers found that people feeling a high degree of hope are more likely to take action, and have the ability to figure out ways to reach their desired goals (Snyder, 2000; Snyder et al., 2002). They have a greater capacity for constructive thinking about how to deal with the problems (Drach-Zahavy and Somech 2002).

The concept of hope is a strong motivational force which seems to give young people the energy to act even in the absence of certainties (Courville and Piper 2004; McGeer, 2004). Hope may also motivate social engagement. Ojala (2012b) carried out research to investigate if hope concerning climate change has a significant relation to pro-environmental behavior as well as an impact on behavior when controlling for already well-known predictors such as values, social influence, knowledge, and gender. This study concluded that it is important to try to avoid extreme cynicism concerning, for example, politicians, and scientists, since this often leads to feelings of helplessness. When people start to do something concrete it seems as if hope is evoked by the actions themselves (Ojala, 2012b). Finding ways to instill hope for the environment in young people could be vital as a motivational force. STEP should offer some positivity over what can be achieved (without raising expectations falsely or too highly) to promote engagement. Promoting positive relationships with local Policy Makers and giving YEC some understanding of the difficulties of their role may help to alleviate pessimism or cynicism and may also help to promote trust.

5.1.2.3 Trust

While STEP is a platform that allows Policy Makers to quickly open up their policy and project proposals to young people, it might be important to consider that this process should not be seen as unilateral. There is skepticism on the side of the Young people as to what the intentions of policy makers really are. Existing literature also shows that when it comes to the environment, young people trust scientists and established NGOs (Brewer and Ley, 2013) much more than politicians. Scientists are widely trusted across the EU, with Greeks, Estonians, French and Finns in particular naming this source as trustworthy. In particular students and those who have spent the longest time in full-time education – ie groups that are likely to place their trust in rational reasoning based on facts – are most likely of all to have confidence in scientists. Half or more than half

of Austrian, German and Swedish respondents say they trust environmental NGOs in environmental issues (European Commission, 2008).

The interview data shows that Young People are quite mistrustful of people in Authority, and that the level of mistrust seems to increase with the level of power of the Policy Maker. Young People generally felt that their opinions and actions would not make any difference. The popularity of the politician was perceived to be what mattered more to them, not pro-environmental action or the concerns of younger people. If the actions of the policy maker could be seen to be 'popular' and perhaps win them votes then they may take it, but not for altruistic reasons. Economic benefit was also felt to be much more of a priority than the environment to politicians. Mistrust in politics was common amongst all the young people we interviewed, with the general opinion that politicians just repeat the same mistakes.

*“An obstacle is that politicians don't give us much of their time, they are thinking of their own opportunity not about Young People.” Politicians need to be more in touch with Young People and citizens; to be more willing to introduce new policies so people can see the effect. “
Spanish YEC*

Young people from some countries seemed to display a deeper, more ingrained mistrust of politicians than others, with corruption being mentioned as common in some countries. They expressed how difficult it was for public institutions to regain trust once it had been breached. A feeling that politicians are quite disconnected from the reality of everyday lives of ordinary people was also common. **Feelings of disengagement from the process of Policy Making** at the European level were also expressed by some young people.

“I think that the most important thing is the mistrust about all the public institutions, it's very difficult to regain trust and form links”. Spanish YEC

Research shows that British young people are **more trusting of Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) than of state political institutions**. This trend can also be seen across Europe, (Mahendran and Cook, 2007). Our data seems to back this up, as the young people interviewed discussed the perceived different relationships held between themselves and those in a higher level of power (working in the 'big building' / City Hall) and those working more in contact with citizens in one of the cultural centres for example, the former being negative ('they are like aliens & not in touch with us'), the latter positive ('more like us, a friend even').

“Most of these civic centres, they have their working quarters in the civic buildings. They work with young people every day. People in the City Hall - it's like some kind of alien. Should involve the people who are closer to them such as the civic centre workers. “ Spanish YEC

Many young people also feel a lack of trust over the impact their actions may have, some had become more involved in political action on environmental issues recently via **petitions** following their widespread appearance on many **social media** websites. The general feeling was that despite the awareness raising benefits that these petitions sites can bring, their impact on actual policy is much less dramatic.

“You can sign as many petitions as you like, but it doesn't seem to have any real effect. I have used Change.org, 38 degrees and Avaaz regularly. Anyone can set up a petition, I have seen petitions that I have been involved in then get discussed in parliament, but often there are only about 10 people in parliament, they are never discussed at peak times. It's an illusion of democracy.” UK YEC

Trust in sources outside of oneself, for instance, trust in technology and trust in environmental organizations was identified by Ojala (2012b) as having a direct bearing on feelings of hope concerning the global environment. If the technology we are developing for the project to support environmental policy making (i.e.

the STEP platform) is to have an impact for young people, it must be both trusted and offer the hope of making a difference in the future.

5.1.3 Summary: Key Diagnosis Points from Interviews

In the EU, “participation in democratic life” is considered to be a fundamental right recognized by Article 10.3 of the Lisbon Treaty of 2007 and an inherent part of the European citizenship provisions. Focusing more specifically on young European citizens, the same treaty emphasizes in Article 165 the importance of “encouraging the development of youth exchanges and of exchanges of socioeducational instructors, and encouraging the participation of young people in democratic life in Europe.” Other recent research via Interviews with stakeholders, focus groups and survey results reveal that there is a clear and growing dissatisfaction with the way politics is conducted and with ‘politicians’ in general (EACA 2010 – Youth Participation in Democratic Life).

While young citizens are the most likely to criticise the state of their political systems and apparently disengage from it, they are also the most likely – to a significant degree – to hold extremely ambitious and idealist notions about what democratic participation should be like and about how involved they actually say they want to be (Bruter and Harrison, 2009). If this is the case, then STEP should have ample reason and incentive to provide young people with an opportunity to become more involved with the Environmental Policy decision making process. It also seems relevant to focus our effort on using methods familiar to young people to promote this engagement; the impact of sites such as Facebook and Twitter on young people’s civic engagement has been studied (e.g., Brandtzaeg et al., 2012; 2015) and a set of guidelines to facilitate civic engagement via social media among young people was developed by Dasgupta (2011). These will not be discussed here in depth but will be considered in D 4.2. In addition to considering existing guidelines regarding youth engagement, our interview data and qualitative research data enable us to provide a few key points of relevance to increase engagement with Environmental Issues and Civic Participation in Young People. These are generally in agreement with the aforementioned guidelines.

STEP Key Diagnosis Points:

- Inform on Relevant Issues (update regularly)
- Promote Trust (trust with higher level Policy Makers will need to be earned)
- Promote self efficacy (their actions should be felt to ‘make a difference’)
- Inform on Participation (they should know HOW to get involved)
- Participation should be as quick & easy as possible (lower the barrier for getting involved)
- Start Small & Local (More achievable results, promotes positivity)
- Promote Optimism/Hope for the future (with realistic targets)
- Promote Pan-European Discussion (It’s possible to learn from other countries)
- Avoid cynicism regarding politics (Not an easy job, sometimes tough decisions necessary)
- Promote Collective mentality (Together we can make a difference)
- Promote a ‘Young Environment’ for participation (Capture the energy and enthusiasm of Youth)

6 STEP Cultural Probe

To ensure the tool we are developing is suited to the needs of the young people who are the intended users it is vital that we listen to them and find out as much as possible about them and their interest in environmental issues. User Centred Design (Norman, 2013) puts the User at the heart of the Design Process and has methods that help the Service or system Designer understand the user needs and what they wish to achieve by using the system/service. The International Usability Standard, ISO 13407, specifies the principles and activities that underlie user centred design:

1. The design is based upon an explicit understanding of users, tasks and environments.
2. Users are involved throughout design and development.
3. The design is driven and refined by user-centred evaluation.
4. The process is iterative.
5. The design addresses the whole user experience.
6. The design team includes multidisciplinary skills and perspectives.

Our initial interview work for D 2.2 was conducted to enable us to develop a deeper understanding of our user and to develop scenarios and personas to inform the development of the software following the User Centred Design process described above. Task 4.1 discussed in this deliverable is about understanding youth motivation for participation, the interviews were helpful to inform us about this, but we wished to develop a deeper understanding regarding youth engagement.

The main instrument for the research conducted under the auspices of task 4.1 has been a digital cultural probe. Originally the idea of using a probe for this research was done with diverse purposes. Since the project works alongside pilot partners in diverse European countries we wanted to have a research instrument we could flexibly use across contexts and came to the conclusion that a Probe could support this. Secondly, because the goal of STEP is to create a web/mobile platform we wanted a research instrument that could generate inspirational data for the design of the platform while at the same time addressing problems of design related with the engagement of young people with environmental issues via the STEP platform.

6.1 Use of Cultural Probes

The cultural probe is a research technique originally devised by Gaver et al. (1999). It is a technique which includes open-ended and evocative activities for participants to pursue in their own time to help narrate and depict their lives to researchers and technology designers. Gaver and colleagues first developed the cultural probe method as part of a collaborative approach to designing innovative technologies for the home and worked with the elderly in different European countries. The aim was to help better integrate older participants into the everyday life of their communities. As the researchers of the study were geographically dispersed and unable to immerse themselves in the communities for long periods of time, they developed what they called a 'cultural probe', a design-oriented way to acquire inspirational glimpses of the lives of communities targeted for design.

Cultural Probe, participants often self-report on their activities and the Cultural Probe 'toolkit' is usually based on the creation of a kit containing material to aid and inspire this **self-reporting** (such as a disposable camera, maps and/or a diary). The data it generates is heterogeneous and serves the primary purpose of being **inspirational for design activities**. Probes are **design oriented** and have an **exploratory goal**. They are used for exploring new opportunities rather than for solving known problems (Mattelmäki, 2005). A review of how

cultural probes have been adopted by the Human Computer Interaction (HCI) community was carried out by Boehner et al. (2007), and they argue that cultural probes are not simply “another technique” for getting data, but rather frame an alternative account of knowledge production in HCI design.

Since their original conception back in 1999, the cultural probe method has grown to encompass a large and diverse field of research. The application of ‘Cultural Probe’ approaches to investigate issues other than those for which it was originally designed has led to the production of several kinds of so-called ‘X-Probes’ (Boehner et al. 2007). These divergent probes have been widely used in the field of HCI and Social Science research, and have been labelled according to their use, for example:

- Technology probes: are a particular type of probe that combine the social science goal of collecting information about the use and the users of the technology in a real- world setting, the engineering goal of field-testing the technology, and the design goal of inspiring users and designers to think of new kinds of technology to support their needs and desires. A well-designed technology probe should balance these different disciplinary influences (Hutchinson et al., 2003).
- Domestic probes: designed to provoke, reveal and capture the motivational forces that shape an individual and his or her home life (Hemmings et al., 2002).
- Cognitive probes: designed to provoke reflection on lifestyle choices, e.g. food/exercise choices (Mamykina et al., 2006).
- Empathy probes: instead of ‘probing for inspiration’ the focus is on ‘probing for empathy’, being able to identify with issues and concerns, for example within the family (Horst et al., 2004).

More recently, Wallace et al. (2013) in the paper ‘Making Design Probes Work’ described probes as ‘*directed craft objects used in empathic engagements with individuals around issues centered on self-identity and personal significance*’. This definition clearly fitted the remit for the use of probes in the STEP study, with our aim being to increase our understanding of how young people engage with issues of the environment that are significant to them.

The recruitment of participants for the probe is particularly important for the success of the activity and as such the probe is thought to be a risky technique. Indeed the probe requires participants to spend considerable time in conducting the self-reporting and the probe relies heavily on the motivation of participants to take the time needed and conduct the data collection. In addition the researchers have limited control over the daily reporting activities. Researchers report that it can be hard to motivate participants to do the tasks, as well as to get them to send the physical probes (such as postcards & cameras) back. Success using probes is certainly not guaranteed and it is often necessary to conducted several follow up activities with participants to motivate and support them.

In the case of the STEP Digital Probe the researcher who set up the Cultural Probe (known from here as the Challenge Owner) would take on the role of motivator and encourage participants to complete the tasks by doing some herself and giving supportive feedback on the posts made. The Challenge owner was able to offer technical support if any issues were encountered and give advice on anything else they may need to ask about.

6.1.1 STEP Probe Design and User Enrolment

The cultural probe for STEP has been designed as a digital one. In particular the project took advantage of the prototype STEP platform developed by project partner Kairos (commercial product is known as co:tunity) which offers tools and concepts which were deemed of excellent quality for the conduction of a digital process of self-reporting. In particular:

D4.1 : Youth Motivation Strategies

Promote Collective mentality (Together we can make a difference)

Promote a 'Young Environment' for participation (Capture the energy and enthusiasm of Youth)

The concept of challenge which allow us to engage a number of users in set tasks

The opportunity to upload pictures and other material (audio/video links)

The fact that we could create the accounts for participants hence reducing the barrier to participation

The possibility for participants to comment and award likes to other participants entries

Further Details regarding the prototype STEP platform can be viewed in the STEP Deliverable D2.2 section 3.1.1 E-participation (page 55). A more visual overview of the platform can also be seen on the co:tunity website at the following link <http://www.cotunity.com/>

Cultural probes are usually aimed at a low number of participants (often between 6-8); in order to support a sufficient number of returns we invited 16 participants to the probe in the expectations that at least half would accept and complete the various challenges. For the enrolment of participants we relied on some existing contacts (n= 8) who were former interviewees who had expressed strong motivation for further participation in the project, as well as on pilot city partners for the recruitment of additional participants (n=8). We released 16 invitations in the expectation to receive full participation for at least half of participants. The number of initial acceptances was 14 with one person then dropping out prior to starting the challenge due to time limitations leaving us with 13 participants. Due to the high motivation of participants our uptake was larger than anticipated, but we thought that to maintain the interest of participants in visiting the platform, having more people to contribute would be very positive for the STEP Probe Challenge.

The STEP Digital Cultural Probe was organized with **challenges** released at weekly time intervals:

Week 1: Log onto the challenge and upload your photo for the profile picture & Upload an image and give a little bit of detail for each the following:

This is something I would like to improve.

This is something I worry about.

This is something that inspires me.

Week 2: Upload an image (taken yourself) for the following and comment as before:

If I were the mayor of my town/city this is what I would do.

This is how I usually travel.

This is what I did today for the environment.

This is something I personally could do better.

Upload a map and/or image of the area where you live, or somewhere in your country you like to visit, that is of environmental importance to you.

Week 3: Upload an image and comment to address the following questions:

In my opinion, the best way to get others to join in environmental action is to:

If I were President / Prime Minister of my country my first action for the environment would be: For this you can choose to upload a video / audio file if you prefer.

Where in your city are decisions about the environment made. Where should they be made? And by whom?: You can highlight on a map or add a photo, or both – whatever you prefer.

The following task is optional: Create a meme to highlight one of the environmental issues you have raised in the challenge & upload.

Week one tasks were a gentle introduction to the platform, allowing the participants to upload their photo and to post to give us an idea about the issues that concerned them, what they would like to improve and what inspires them. The second week asked about how they usually travel (although the topic had been raised by some in week one from the initial prompts) and asked about an **action** that they made for the environment. We wanted to get a feel for where locally they felt was important / somewhere they liked to visit and then to discuss what areas of their life they felt they could do better. The issue of leadership was introduced in week two with the young people letting us know what they would do to improve their local area if they had the power to change things as the mayor. Week 3 further developed this leadership and power to change theme asking them a similar question, but on a larger scale, i.e. at the country level what would they do if they were the prime minister/president. This theme continued by asking them about where decisions are currently made in their region and by whom. We wanted to know how they thought others could be motivated to become involved in environmental issues, asking them what the best way would be to do this. In addition to these core tasks, we wanted to know if the participants were keen to complete extra tasks of their own accord.

During the Cultural Probe Challenge it was decided that the participants could also contribute to an analytical phase, and give greater accuracy for what they deemed 'relevant'. The STEP platform allowed posts to be tagged with themes and also to assign a 'relevance' score (1-10). The challenge owner tagged posts with keywords at regular intervals and from the posts and keywords it was apparent that certain themes emerged which were created within the platform. These themes could be selected and all relevant posts displayed along with a template for further analysis (Consequences - see Figure 12) . The platform allows participants to plot a graph (by simply dragging points on a pre-plotted graph) to chart impact & predictability of the trend.

6.1.2 Issues and mitigations

As previously noted the probe is a "risky" technique as it relies entirely on the will of participants to engage with the content and there is risk of a low rate return. During the conduction of the probe we encountered a number of issues and preventive and corrective action have been taken along the process. Initial technical problems were encountered for people logging onto the challenge for the first time, when signing into STEP then there was an option for a quicker social media sign-in, if this option was taken by the participants, it became very difficult for them to then locate the challenge. The challenge owner had to give further details emphasizing the need to log in using the same email account that the challenge invitation was sent to. Some participants were clearly more motivated to do the challenges than others, some prompting to complete the tasks was required for some participants, but the largest problem was due to the initial sign-up procedure for joining the Challenge. The original plan was for the probe to run for 3 weeks after the release of the invitations, however due to the initial sign up problems resulting in a delay for some of the participants in starting the challenge, it was decided to extend the period by a week to ten days to allow people sufficient time to complete the tasks.

6.1.3 Results: Reflections Evoked by the Probe Challenge Tasks

By the end of the Challenge period a total of 143 posts were made to the prototype STEP platform, of these posts 14 were made by the challenge owner/ other STEP researcher. Of the 13 people starting the challenge, all made posts for the tasks given for the first week. Ten People completed a significant proportion of the tasks for all 3 weeks. The role adopted by the challenge owner aimed to increase the motivation of the participants, to set example posts and to comment on posts made by the participants and promote others to do the same. All the questions generated interesting and thought provoking posts which contained visually appealing images that contributed to the overall aesthetic and increased interest and engagement with the platform.

D4.1 : Youth Motivation Strategies

Participants made many comments on other people's posts, with some posts generating some good discussions. Topics generating the most comments were on Sustainable Transport. The theme of better sustainable transport was frequently mentioned in the 'this is something I would like to improve' post & 'this is something I worry about' suggesting that this is an issue of concern for YEC's. Recycling was also discussed often, with ideas for using recycled objects emerging as a theme (under the 'this is something that inspires me' task).

Figure 2 - Screenshot of the most commented posts (numbers = number of comments).

Other subjects generating discussion were about more unusual topics such as how trees in urban areas can be removed and re-planted using specialist equipment. The differences existing between the EU countries was discussed, with participants often asking how things were in other places, they seemed genuinely interested in the similarities and differences. In addition to discussing their home country, participants often commented on things they had noticed in other countries that they had visited so the discussion was not limited to just the countries that the participants resided in. It was interesting to see examples of the participants asking questions of the others and stimulating discussion on certain topics. Others were also very keen on commenting and adding to the conversation.

6.1.3.1 Worries / Concerns.

The Questions asking about what issues were of concern to the participants led to varied responses, helping to improve the understanding we had from the interview data, it was interesting to see the commonalities and differences between the different countries. The themes were quite wide ranging, including pollution, lack of sustainable transport, issues over food and how it is produced and sold (including excess packaging, pesticides, effects on bees etc). Other posts were about traffic levels and air pollution and global warming.

Having insufficient facilities for recycling was mentioned to be a problem in Turkey. More specific worries about cigarette litter were mentioned (Italy), but this post also contained a good solution for how the problem could be dealt with (see image 4 of Figure 3 below).

Figure 3 - Examples of posts about worries/concerns.

6.1.3.2 Improvement

Two of the questions asked the participants to reflect on something they could improve; the first was about a more personal understanding of what action they thought they themselves could change. Posts reflected on personal actions such as walking or cycling more, not using plastic bottles for water, buying products with less packaging, and reducing their energy/ water consumption.

The second was a more general question and tended to evoke responses about improving local facilities for recycling, having better control over energy and better access to sustainable transport. Improving the level of pollution was also mentioned, for both air quality (tying in with the need for better sustainable transport and energy policies) and of litter and industrial pollution both of the local urban area and of the sea and rivers nearby the participants. Other examples (such as the final post in Figure 4) gave examples of quite specific recycling, in this case of vegetable oil that could be turned into Biodiesel and used in sustainable transport.

Figure 4 - Examples of posts discussing Improvement

It was interesting to see the participants interact and begin to ask questions of the others and to stimulate discussion on certain topics. Discussions about Transport, Recycling and Pollution were most frequent, but other more unusual posts also provoked responses from the other participants, ideas for crafting using recycled materials were quite popular (often emerging from the 'this is something that inspires me' post) especially with the female participants (although males did also like or comment on some of these posts).

6.1.3.3 Action

The question asking about an action they had done for the environment evoked posts on issues such as recycling (several posts), upcycling, and saving water. The post on upcycling prompted comments from several other participants, then a flurry of other posts suggesting ideas for both green Christmas gifts and on upcycling and creative ways to make use of recycled material that would otherwise be thrown away. Choosing environmentally friendly products such as cleaning products and clothes was mentioned. Another post on action mentioned investing in a Community Supported Agriculture programme.

“As I have mentioned in a post before, I strongly believe that being careful with what we buy and where we buy from, can make a big difference regarding environmental protection. In addition, this spring I decided to sign up of the Community Supported Agriculture program, that consists in receiving weekly one box of vegetables from a local ecological producer. Therefore, we, as consumers support the small sustainable farmers and the local food production, which is essential for local development, conserving biodiversity and keeping the environment healthy. We also assure the farmer that he is going to sell everything that

he produces. Moreover, we share the risks with the farmer in case something does not grow, but we also get more if there is big production.” *Romanian YEC (Living in the Czeck Republic)*

Figure 5 - Examples of posts showing environmental actions taken

The idea of actions also prompted a post to inform the other participants about practical ways to reduce climate change (Figure 6), the participant reflected on how many of these actions she carried out, saying she could do better and asked the other participants to do the same.

30 THINGS YOU CAN DO TO COMBAT CLIMATE CHANGE

1. Refuse plastic bags when shopping
2. Use the urban containers for recycling paper, glass and plastic
3. Use the green points to improve the quality of recycling
4. Reuse, repair and adapt objects before throwing them
5. Separate the organic matter and, if possible, compost
6. Insulate windows and doors to increase energy efficiency
7. Adjust the temperature of the heating and air conditioning
8. Replace appliances with more efficient models
9. Disconnect all the electronic devices when not in use
10. Boil the water and just use lids to heat it before
11. Reduce water consumption by one third of the consumption goes down the toilet
12. reuse the rainwater to wash the car or water the plants
13. Turn off lights when not needed and renew bulbs
14. Betting operators electric boost renewable energy
15. Extending Outdoor and washing clothes at low temperature
16. Eat less meat: livestock is a major pollutant
17. Eat more seasonal products and zero kilometer
18. Choose organic food and avoid processed food
19. Drink bottled water sparingly
20. Plant trees and exercise extreme caution to prevent fires
21. Buy wooden stamps, which ensure a sustainable source
22. Print only what is essential, and both sides of the paper
23. Reducing the consumption of dishes and plastic cutlery and disposable napkins
24. Reduce labor and travel opted for videoconferencing
25. Leave the car at home and prioritize public transport and bicycles
26. Buy an electric vehicle or share it with others
27. Increase the knowledge to know what science says
28. Push governments to implement policies that respect
29. Choose vacations and getaways that respect the environment
30. Protecting biodiversity and preserving endangered species

How many of these things do you do? I do just 20 things, I can be better.

Figure 6 - Examples of spontaneous post showing actions to combat climate change

6.1.3.4 Inspiration

The posts on inspiration were wide ranging, several posted about natural and coastal habitats and mentioned how it helped relax and inspire them.

“For me the beach has always been a place of peace. I love standing in the cold tide and letting the waves wash around my ankles. The beach inspires my inner creativity and love for the world “ UK YP.

The need to escape city life and connect to the environment was a common theme. Others were inspired by ideas for reusing waste products, another had seen an unusual machine for transplanting trees in operation in Turkey. One participant was an organic farmer who felt inspired by how his produce and work was valued by others, he felt the effort was worthwhile to maintain high quality produce and to collaborate to maintain a good environment. Inspiration was also mentioned as a way to encourage others to engage with environmental issues.

Figure 7 - Examples of posts on Inspiration³

6.1.3.5 Encouraging Others

The posts made for encouraging others to act were very interesting, themes mentioned were: inspiration, education, setting a good example, promoting small changes /habits, talking to others to encourage them (or even buying them a drink). The theme of promoting good habits was quite strong, getting schools involved, not only in education but in action such as the beach clean-up mentioned in the post below. Another post mentioned a similar clean-up activity that had taken place in Calabria (Italy), the participants felt that these activities were an excellent way to engage people and promote environmental action. One of the participants mentioned showing positive results and rewarding people for positive action:

“In my opinion, the best way to get other to join in environmental actions it to either show the positive results of what was and will be done or even reward people for joining in said actions using give away prizes. This approach should not only turn helping the environment into a positive activity for the participants and the nature but also cultivate a good attitude and habits toward said activities in the long term.”

³ Occasionally probe participants have posted images taken from the Internet, for reporting purposes in this deliverable we have replaced fully copyrighted images with equivalent Creative Commons Images. The first image in Figure 7 is a Creative Commons licenced image, that replaces one posted by a participant – source https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reuse#/media/File:Plastic_Bottles_and_LED_Lights_repurposed_as_a_chandelier_during_Ramadan_in_Muslim_Quarter,_Jerusalem_2011.jpg (author Victorgrigas, CC-BY-SA 3.0).

Figure 8 - Examples of posts Encouraging Environmental Action ⁴

6.1.3.6 Leadership

Some of the tasks presented in week 2 & 3 were about promoting the idea of leadership among young people and supporting their empowerment in environmental action and asked:

- If I were the Mayor of my town this is what I would do.
- If I were President / Prime Minister of my country my first action for the environment would be (a bit like the mayor task, but think bigger!).

⁴ First image replaced with equivalent creative commons – source https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Illuminated_Cristmass_tree_made_of_bottles.jpg (author Yuval Y. CC-GFDL)

D4.1 : Youth Motivation Strategies

The wording of the question was important; it was better to frame the question in the first person – asking specifically what they themselves would do, rather than asking about what the mayor of their town or PM of their country should do. This type of question promotes greater self-reflection and is likely to increase the motivation to engage with the question that the latter example.

The responses were thoughtful insights as to what could be achieved at both a local and national level, local topics covered improving access into cities for sustainable methods of transport, cleaning up suburban sidewalks to increase walking and improve the local areas, regional actions included rewarding towns/cities for using cleaner methods of transport, giving tax incentives for renewable/alternative energy investments and for those reducing food waste. Others mentioned repealing laws allowing the sun's energy to be taxed by the government. Setting good examples as leaders was also mentioned as was education and awareness raising, and rewarding environmental behaviours.

Figure 9 - Examples of posts Promoting Leadership⁵

⁵ Original third image above replaced with equivalent creative commons image – source https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/BCI_Bus#/media/File:Bci_buses.jpg (author Michelenazzari, CC-BY-SA 3.0)

6.1.3.7 Decision Making

The next question about decision making was also about reflecting on leadership, but aimed to understand how effective YP think the current situation is in their local area.

Where in your city are decisions about the environment made. Where should they be made? And by whom?

This question showed that young people do indeed want to have their voices heard and that in some cases there is not an effective mechanism in place currently to allow this to happen. Some of the participants (from Mollet del Vallès, Spain) felt that the system was open and transparent and that there was already a good decision making process in place; citizen’s views on the environment were being taken into account. Some participants reflected that their local municipalities had made some good decisions recently (Valdemoro and Mollet), and one participant from Valdemoro (Spain) mentioned that in this coming year their government had promised more opportunity for citizens to voice their concerns regarding environmental issues. Conversely in other countries (Italy) it was felt that leaders were too attached to the ‘old mentality’ and despite a recent ‘special focus’ on citizen participation that the ideas generated remained ‘mostly words’ due to bureaucracy.

Where in my city are decisions about the environment made

In my city (Valdemoro) the decisions about environment are made in this building and are made by people from the city council. In the last five years they have made good decisions as closing some factories which were nearby and were polluting too much.

The problem is that they do not let citizens give their opinion and most of the times the decisions are based on economic interests. The new government has promised that next year there will be a point for citizens to give opinion and show what the concerns about environment are.

Where in your city are decisions about the environment made. Where should they be made? And by whom?

In my city all the decisions are made in the city hall. There are the mayor and the different councillors with the experts. So there exists an environmental councillor that deals with these issues. Approximately every month all the government of the city meets in a public plenary where explains the decisions they have made. Moreover, when the city budget is preparing is open to any suggestions of the citizens as well as you can send an email with your ideas in any moment of the year. Sometimes the city hall organise meetings with those citizen that want to participate in specific issues talking and recommending how to fix some problems or how to prepare a public policy associated. I have to say that my city hall is open enough and I have had a good experience when I have participated. I believe my city has a good make decision system.

Where in your city are decisions about the environment made. Where should they be made? And by whom?

Decisions about environment are made in the town hall here in Heraklion, Greece. I strongly believe that environmental issues are part of the political system so I wouldn't suggest another place to make decisions like that. Although environmental decisions should be taken into consultation to citizens and political leaders should guarantee the application of those issues. I can't any way to do that, as I can't think any way to control decisions of political leaders, especially here in Greece. The only thing I can think about is for citizens take seriously into consideration the environmental problem because human being is also part of nature.

The decisions on environmental problems in Dundee are made on meetings of the environment committee in the City Chambers, City Square, Dundee, DD1 3BY. I think that it is a good location though, the city council building would be more suitable for the committee.

Figure 10 - Examples of posts on Decision Making ⁶

Trend	Average Significance	No of Posts
Sustainable Transport	8.3	33
Recycling	8.1	37
Reducing Waste	8.0	40
Energy Saving	8.0	13
Local Environment	7.8	44
Pollution	7.7	35
Natural Habitats	7.7	23
Climate Change	7.6	23
Making Decisions	7.4	25
Saving Water	7.1	9
Sustainable Agriculture	7.0	18
Redevelopment Urban Land	6.9	5

Table 1 - Trends Identified from the posts and their average significance

⁶ images 1-3 for local Town Halls replaced with creative commons licence images – source image 1 <https://www.flickr.com/photos/martius/8086491990> (author M. Vicente, CC-BY-SA 2.0); image 2 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mollet_del_Valles (author JT Curses, CC-BY-Sa 4.0); image 3 https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Venetian_Loggia,_Heraklion_02.jpg (author Bernard Gagnon, CC-BY-SA 3.0).

Figure 11 - An example of a discussion generated by a sustainable transport post

6.1.3.8 Co-Analysis of Posts by Participants

As the number of posts increased and themes emerged, the challenge owner thought it would be useful to get more opinions on these themes from the participants themselves and to see which posts they thought were more relevant than others. The request for participants to contribute to this analysis was an optional one. Five participants contributed to at least one theme analysis, with some contributing to several different themes, such as sustainable transport (5 participants), sustainable agriculture (4), local environment (3), recycling (3), climate change (2) and reducing waste (2). Some participants also filled in the text boxes of the 'co:nsequence' tree to give more detailed information regarding these emerging themes (the Challenge owner had filled in the first few for an example). Once the participants had been given co-analyst rights then they were also able to tag posts (both their own and those of the other participants). Several participants also tagged the posts and this contributed to the richness of the data generated. About a third of the participants were extremely engaged with the platform, contributing more than what they had been asked to do to gain their reward and interacting with others on the platform regularly. Another third carried out all the tasks they were asked to do and made rich contributions, but did not show the same level of enthusiasm as the 'very

motivated' group. The remaining third made some valuable contributions, but did not (for whatever reason) quite manage to complete all of the tasks.

Figure 12 – Examples of Trend Analysis on the STEP platform showing the contributions from participants

Figure 13 - Screenshot showing the Trends emerging from the posts (number of tags in brackets)

6.1.4 General Level of Engagement with the Cultural Probe

Given the busy lifestyles of young people and the fact that the participants were all studying or working, we were very pleased with the level of activity and engagement that the Cultural Probe Challenge generated. Three did not manage to complete all the tasks, with one or two of these three not progressing past the first week challenges, this is to be expected in a task requiring commitment and being time-consuming. However, the high level of engagement shown by the majority of the participants was very encouraging and that the cultural probe confirms that the prototype STEP platform is an excellent tool to be used as the foundation for the final platform.

The primary aim of using the STEP platform was to conduct a Digital Cultural Probe, allowing us to receive useful and relative information about how young people perceive and engage with environmental issues and to allow us to have a 'glimpse' of their everyday lives. Having easy access to photo uploading and posting was really useful, and the fact that the platform had similarities to some Social Networking sites such as Facebook made it quite intuitive. However, there were a few differences, which did cause some minor usability issues. Once the participants were enrolled and familiarized with the Challenge on STEP then they did engage well and provided us with useful data to inform the STEP project about the engagement of young people with environmental issues.

The secondary aim was to see how STEP would perform when using it with a group of young people. It was very useful to find out at an early stage about any potential usability issues and to be able to report back and have these issues ironed out before a larger scale study takes place with the Pilot Partners.

The platform is well designed and aesthetically pleasing. We will be conducting some follow up interviews shortly with a subsection of participants to give us more qualitative data of their experience using the platform and to probe a bit more into issues they encountered during the activity. The Challenge owner received many emails after the completion of the study from participants stating this and asking if they could be kept informed about the Project and the future development of the platform. Examples of email messages are shown below.

"It was a pleasure to complete this challenge. I enjoyed a lot, met new people and environmental habits and learned how to improve my actions to help environment. Thank you so much for making this challenge possible and helping us so much. It was really nice of you. Best, XX "

“ I would like to be informed, if possible, if such a platform will work in the future. I would be up for contributing. I wish you a wonderful night XX”

7 Strategic Recommendations

The use of ICT can be considered to facilitate political participation, however, it cannot be expected that technology use per se can have a direct impact on political decision making and / or on active citizen participation. Ensuring that the voices are heard by the decision makers and have an impact on political decisions is as important as providing a usable e-Participation platform.

Previous sections of the deliverable were devoted to an analysis of the situation and it is possible now to consider some of the key critical outcomes of this work. In this section we distill a number of strategic recommendations for action that emerged from the diagnosis of the situation for STEP. These recommendations could be implemented in the piloting phase of WP5. It needs also to be specified again that in the perspective used here a strategy (Rumelt, 2011) is an experiment based on testing and designing some sort of hypothesis for action based on the current knowledge of the situation. The recommendations offered here should be seen as hypothesis, they may prove successful during the testing phase but they may also prove not to work as expected. It will be therefore important for the consortium to apply critical and strategical thinking in the piloting phase when working on these hypotheses. However, it would also be important to test them in the pilots and learn for future application of the final platform. We divide the recommendations in two: high level recommendations that work more at a conceptual level and low level recommendations that work more at a practical and applied level. We have also considered other research and reports on e-participation (with a particular focus on participation within the EU). We discuss the challenges raised by the implementation of e-participation tools and recommendations to try and overcome these issues, in particular we identify key steps and timing and relevant digital media and marketing techniques to achieve maximum youth engagement and reach during the pilots. It is expected that having access to the STEP platform will reduce the transaction costs (mostly time and effort) associated with participation and enable young people to contribute to the policy making process in a much more accessible way. We believe that the importance of developing a Sense of Community within the project and the e-Participation platform is crucial to the overall success of the project and this should be nurtured as much as possible both at the Pilot level and the wider project level.

7.1 Overall principles of e-Participation

Certain crucial aspects are common to all e-participation processes.

These are:

• Alignment with young people’s realities

e-participation processes need to be aligned with young people’s lives. This relates to matters such as content, information and time management, but also to design and technical implementation.

The processes should be designed to interest, stimulate and motivate young people to ensure their continuing involvement.

• Resources

e-participation processes require sufficient resources such as expertise, time, funding and technology, as well as staff to provide guidance and advisory services.

• Effectiveness & direct influence

e-participation processes need to have an outcome. A structural link to decision-making processes is essential.

• Transparency

the overall process needs to be transparent for everyone. This requirement extends to all information related to the process as well as to the software and tools used.

• End-to-end involvement of young people |

young people need to be involved in all stages of the process. This includes a feedback option in all phases of the process.

Specific Challenges:

According to the recent European Parliament Report (Potential and Challenges of E-Participation in the European Union, 2016) one of the biggest challenges for e-participation is European citizens' disinterest in EU politics, including the lack of trust in the EU (and the belief that the EU cannot solve their problems). This also represents a more general challenge since e-participation tools tend to have a very low participation rate at national levels. The other significant challenge is that these e-participation tools are simply unknown to citizens. The first issue is quite difficult to address and will take time and probably many positive engagement experiences to change; the second can be addressed much more easily by Awareness Raising and informing Young People in a timely and appropriate way about how to engage with the STEP platform to ensure their voice is heard.

7.1.1 High Level Recommendations for the strategy,

From our User Research we recommend the following:

-
- ACTION OVER ATTITUDE: Environmental Action over environmental engagement as an attitude should be the strategic guiding concept for STEP.
 - AVOID DEMOGRAPHICS: Avoid focusing interventions on demographics or social factors driving engagement as an attitude as these are outside the control of the STEP project.
 - AVOID EXCLUSION: Limit emphasis of interventions on certain factors that are antecedents of good engagement as this risks the exclusion of entire categories, based on socio-economic factors or geographical location.
 - DESIGN FOR ACTION: Since there is a gap between positive environmental attitude and environmental action (ie. Positive engagement doesn't necessarily lead to action) the platform design needs to strongly encourage action.
 - SUPPORT NON-ENVIRONMENTALISTS: There are margins for STEP to also support the action of young people who are not necessarily engaged with the environment (ie. They may be interested to contribute to their local area). This reinforces the recommendation of focusing on supporting action rather than engagement as an attitude.

7.1.2 Practical Recommendations (Design and Pilot oriented)

- **FOCUS ON ISSUES OF INTEREST:** Focus the bootstrap-piloting of the platform on the discussion of policies/issues that are of direct interest to YP: transport, food, Reducing Waste /recycling. This is likely to ensure a better and larger participation. Some indication has been given in this report about what issues interest Young People, however Pilot Cities could carry out some further research to ensure that the focus is on issues concerning the local young people to ensure greater interest and engagement.
- **START SMALL AND BUILD UP:** The first e-Participation process conducted should be on a smaller scale and be of a simple nature with clearly defined guidelines. It is important to remember that participation cannot be allowed to lead to indecision: the process of participation has to have a result. Starting with, for example, a simple vote on different options for environmental projects within the area will likely be more successful than starting out with a full blown environmental consultation process. Both the scale and scope of the participation process can be increased as the Pilot study progresses.
- **PROMOTE TRUST:** There is some level of mistrust between young people and policy action at a very general level and this inevitably will reflect on environmental policy and participation of young people. While it's clearly outside the scope of STEP to bridge this gap, some design solutions for the platform may be considered including trust /reputation mechanisms for rating the relevance of proposed policies as well as their implementation. Pilots should ensure that they provide clear guidelines for how participant's input will be used and what feedback will be given to them (including likely timeframes). Allowing participant feedback on the process also promotes trust. Participation should not lead to indecision and final conclusions and feedback should be clear and easy to find. Some Pilot cities have a high level of Trust (Mollet del Vallès and to a lesser degree Valdemoro) the rest have less existing history of citizen e-Participation and Trust will have to be earned. Crete (Greece) was very concerned that Trust may be damaged or lost entirely following any negative first experience with the platform; appropriate user/pilot testing of the platform in conjunction with Pilots following Best Practice Guidelines for e-Participation should help to avoid any issues of this kind. Ensuring the process is as open and transparent as possible should also promote trust building.
- **PROMOTE EMPOWERMENT & LEADERSHIP:** Offer via STEP opportunities for empowerment and leadership: young people should feel that their action is meaningful and helps make a difference. Give feedback; inform young people how their actions have made a difference, state how any information was used and highlight any actions following a consultation. In terms of design this would call for appropriate feedback mechanisms to be included in STEP. Pilot Cities should consider how this could be supported, for example, Locride (Italy) specifically mentioned the inclusion of Youth Leaders in the process.
- **UTILISE APPROPRIATE MECHANISMS** eg reputational mechanisms. Aspects of gamification such as the leaderboard and point system built into STEP should be used to support empowerment and leadership. This will be investigated in more detail via co-creation activities which are part of task 2.3. Mollet del Vallès (Spain) would like the system to recognize the Catalonia citizen ID card, this verification could then be linked to reward mechanisms as well as enabling voting on local issues. This identification process is unlikely to be popular in areas where Trust is not high though, (esp. Turkey, Italy & Greece) so this functionality would need to be optional, also enabling anonymous e-Participation where this is required.

D4.1 : Youth Motivation Strategies

- **NURTURE EXISTING PARTNERSHIPS:** Utilise existing Youth / Environmental Organisations, partnerships; these should be nurtured where possible. In the first place integrate where possible with Youth Environment Europe (YEE) who have over 40,000 members and are partners in the project, but also if possible local NGO's in the pilot municipalities. Pilot Cities should consider how to increase collaboration with relevant organisations, for example in Italy - Civitassolis.org. (a young people's association) - Locride Municipality would like to use this existing channel to embed STEP to get greater reach. Mollet del Vallès has strong ties with the local secondary school and the municipality are keen to retain and nurture this relationship. STEP should aim to forge new partnerships with any environmental and/or youth groups they do not already have a working relationship with.
- **KEEP BARRIERS TO PARTICIPATION LOW:** Make it quick and easy for young people to access the STEP platform from other social media sites, log-in should be optional to view platform content. It is also important to offer a variety of ways to participate, some young people will not be inclined to participate in debates, but they may be willing to vote on issues and/or share material with others online. Allowing them a choice of participation methods will increase engagement.
- **DEVELOP A SENSE OF COMMUNITY:** Some Pilot partners have already made an excellent start with this recommendation. There are no definitive answer as to how to go about this, but questions regarding youth identification and belonging should try and be addressed as a starting point. The ability to create common goals and purpose is important. This ties in with the 'sense of empowerment and efficacy already mentioned and is also linked to trust factors. For the Pilots a good mix of online and offline (real-world) community building events and actions is a good starting point for building up this sense of community among the young citizens.

**D4.1 Suggested Strategical Guiding Policy for STEP:
Maximise Youth Engagement & Participation as
(environmental) ACTION**

Figure 14 Strategical Guiding Policy for STEP.

7.3 Ensuring Effective e-Participation:

According to the IAP2's Public Participation Spectrum the five levels of increasing public engagement are:

- **Inform:** to provide balanced and objective information to support understanding by the public
- **Consult:** To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions
- **Involve:** To work with the public to ensure concerns and aspirations are understood and considered
- **Engage:** To engage with the public on each aspect of the decision, including the development of alternatives and a preferred solution
- **Empower:** To create governance structures to delegate decision-making and/or work directly with the public
-

Brandtzæg et al. (2012) suggest nine recommendations for successful youth civic engagement in social media. The researchers suggest that the key to ensuring that e-Participation does not become a sidelined activity is to move beyond proprietary web platforms toward greater integration with existing social media, integrating e-Participation into the online behaviours of citizens across Europe.

Their recommendations are:

- Find young people where they are. Use the channels they use. In terms of content, for maximum reach, industry experts suggest that a marketer should spread the content around like a digital dandelion. And “the best way to maximize distribution is for the content to live in the places where the target audience is already spending time. Building content bridges from other popular locations to a landing website in order to catch millennials’ attention is proved to be much better than pushing for their attention.
- Create engaging content that is of value to young users.
- Provide engaging layouts and pictures of youth (colourful, contrasts, music, video clips).
- Co-create with the target audience.
- Give the youth ownership or leadership. Allow the youth themselves to create content and respond to youths’ self-created civic engagement.
- Support a "bottom-up" strategy that can create collaboration among youth.
- Welcome responses and contributions. Be quick to respond, and respond appreciatively, to contributions supporting deliberative practices.
- Enable individual expressions and visibility. In particular, support self-expression through photos, video or other rich media. Create an informal and exciting setting. Support flexible, project-oriented micro-participation. Create an easy and convenient venue. Usability and privacy are always important. Re-engineer the sharing model. While all clicks are equal all shares are not. Create tools and features that facilitate involvement, collaboration, deliberation and mobilization
- Create compelling calls to action. Campaigns and contests designed to be promoted in social media

We feel that the STEP platform is well suited to following the above recommendations and the Pilot strategies are well aligned with these principles. We should build upon these recommendations to ensure the success of the project.

7.4 ROADMAP For Pilots :

7.4.1 Action Plan First Phase 1: JULY - SEPTEMBER 2016 (month 14-16)

Raise Awareness / Inform

One of the main elements crucial for the successful implementation of the STEP project and the sustainability of its main outcomes is the maximised participation of young people and other target groups. Pilots should have information available in an accessible format (including not using too much technical language) for the specific topic that they wish to engage young people in discussion about via the STEP platform (See individual plans for each Pilot).

This first promotional video which was created to promote the project and raise awareness is available in the STEP YouTube channel and can be directly accessed via the following link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R90AgFkdnJc> or by searching “STEP Click your environment now”.

7.4.1.1 The main objectives of the STEP activities in the first phase are to:

- Raise awareness of local, regional and national policy makers and public bodies, especially in the environmental field.
- Maximise participation via interaction offered via the STEP platform/ mobile app. Advertise to young people with the use of targeted communication means, integrated in common interaction contexts, such as education, information, entertainment and social networking
- Ensure efficient communication and understanding regarding the project, obtain support and encourage participation of all stakeholders involved, as well as the wider public in disseminating information and exploiting results
- Introduce new patterns of conduct in the target groups – the end users of the project’s main outputs and results
- Integrate targeted approaches, eliciting enhanced networking to disseminate new and sustainable ideas, with the use of innovative and creative means
- Establish formal and non-formal networks, also strengthening and valorising existing ones, for the exchanging of ideas and practices, in order to develop the **sense of a community** in participating in decision making in the fields of environment and sustainable development and the public sphere in general.
- Raise awareness of the youth community (youth organisations, bodies and organisations in the field of youth, formal, informal and non-formal education and training organisations, young people in general).
- Achieve diversity and inclusiveness by involving a demographically balanced group of young people reflecting the community and the community needs.

7.4.1.2 In order to ensure maximum Participation levels

Consider:

- Practical barriers of reach
- Clearly Defining the demographic you need to reach
- Clearly Define Core Teams involved for each Pilot Partner – (shown in table 2 below)

Use Appropriate Tools:

- Social Media (including Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Google+, YouTube) Mass Media (radio, tv) via
- Press Releases at appropriate timings.
- Multi-media tools (STEP video via YouTube & other relevant channels)
- STEP Platform (enable easy sharing of links to STEP via other social media platforms)
- Pilot Local Authority Websites (using the STEP widgets / links to STEP platform)
- STEP QR Code / Posters / Flyers
- Existing Networks of Interest
 - o Newsletters
 - o Events (real-world) at a Pilot Level, including Launch events, Open events
 - o Events (online) eg. Webinars
- Targeted promotional material should be prepared to ensure the maximum dissemination of the project, especially to young people. Prepared items are: business cards, post-its, USB sticks, cloth bags, hats, etc. Each pilot partner is responsible to prepare the design, print and distribute the dissemination material that better meets their own needs, under the supervision of PLANO2.

7.4.3 Individual Pilot Plans for Awareness Raising – Phase 1:

(Modified from D 7.7)

Indicative timeline: Months 14 to 16 (August – September 2016)	
Comune Di Sant’ Agata del Bianco (Locride Italy):	
Core team	Potential members of the core team include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ partner’s project team; ⊗ Civitas Solis Association.
Communication channels & measures	<u>Channels:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ local authority websites (municipality & local associations); ⊗ local mass media & social media ⊗ peer groups. <u>Measures:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ public events & press conferences; ⊗ posters & flyers; ⊗ information points.

Mollet de Valles Municipality, Spain	
Core team	<p>Potential members of the core team include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● partner’s project team (civil servants & councillors); ● Esplai Xivarri; ● Club Muntanyenc; ● Agroecological Association of Gallecs; ● Geoblau (private company specialized in environment and sustainability) ● Consortium of Gallecs; ● LA Era: center for young people ; ● Secondary Schools of the city; ● Participation Census of the City; ● Morats I Torrats (cultural Associations); ● Council of the City (participatory body);
Communication channels & measures	<p><u>Channels:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● local authorities websites (municipality & local associations); ● Local newspapers ● Local TV ● Local radio ● Advertisements in sport facilities ● Secondary schools (mailing, access to classroom) ● local mass media & social media and youth-related websites; Facebook, Twitter <p><u>Measures:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● public events & press conferences (eg at the Summer City Festival & other local events); ● posters & flyers; ● STEP “business cards”; ● information points.
Valdemoro Municipality, Spain	
Core team	<p>Potential members of the core team include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● partner’s project team; ● experts from the targeted stakeholders
Communication channels & measures	<p><u>Channels:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● local authority websites (municipality & local associations); ● youth associations’ forum; ● Centre for Youth Information and Documentation; ● local mass media (TV & radio, thematic publications/issues); <p><u>Measures:</u></p>

D4.1 : Youth Motivation Strategies

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● School & high school activities (7-10 High schools, September Breakfast sessions with Head Teachers); ● Festivities activities; ● Youth activities (Involve 7 Youth Associations and 6 other associations. Include in Demonstrating & Evaluating the STEP platform); ● Other activities (conferences, meetings, etc.); ● Promotional material (Leaflets, posters, hats with STEP Logo, STEP Videos);
Region of Crete, Greece	
Core team	Potential members of the core team include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● partner’s project team; ● experts from the targeted areas (see below).
Communication channels & measures	<u>Channels:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● local authorities websites (municipality & local associations); ● social media – Greek Facebook & Twitter account; ● youth-related websites; ● local mass media (TV & radio, newspapers); <u>Measures:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● public events on all 4 Regional Units (Chania, Heraklion, Rethymno & Lasithi) ● Face to Face meetings with: Members of the Environmental and Spatial Planning Committee & Representatives of other Greek public authorities involved in Environmental Impact Assessments, (e.g.Decentralized Administration of Crete, Municipalities). ● Promotional material - posters & leaflets; USB sticks and post-its.
Hatay Metropolitan Municipality, Turkey	
Core team	Potential members of the core team include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● partner’s project team; ● expert group on environment; ● academics; ● Hatay Smart Eco-City Agency.
Communication channels & measures	<u>Channels:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● local authorities websites (municipality & local associations); ● social media and youth-related websites; ● local mass media (TV & radio, newspapers); <u>Measures:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● conferences; ● eco-city environment festivals; ● surveys; ● promotional material (Leaflets, posters, hats with STEP Logo, STEP Videos).

Table 2: Pilot Plans for Phase 1: Months 14-16 August –September 2016

7.4.3 Action Plan 2nd phase: Months 17-19 (October 2016 – December 2016)

The objective of the 2nd phase of the dissemination strategy is to engage local stakeholders in discussion and interaction, in order to coordinate the organisation of participatory activities for the introduction of young people to the STEP platform. The activities will be targeted to enhance participation from young people at a local level, disseminating the projects objectives, while providing them with the appropriate tools and motivation to actively participate in the project, mainly via the STEP e-Participation platform.

The second phase interactions will be facilitated through local workshops which will take place in each area, organised by members of the core team. Participants will include local stakeholders, representatives of local authorities, public policy bodies and local organisations, etc. The programme of the workshops will include:

- a brief presentation of the STEP project (objectives, outputs, results, etc.) and platform
- brief presentation of the scope and objectives of the relevant local pilot activities;
- each of the presentation of the pilot activities will be followed by a thematic discussion among the participants, aiming to identify ways to enhance youth participation more effectively
- the core teams' experts will facilitate discussions and guide the formation of a draft agenda for the organisation of participatory activities to enhance youth participation
- 2-3 participatory activities (using the tools provided in the 1st Dissemination Plan)

Pilots should work with young people to ensure that the concerns and aspirations raised are understood and considered. According to the report - Youth Participation in Democratic Life (EACEA 2010/03 | January 2013) motivation to participate further, in the view of both stakeholder experts interviewed as well as young people, comes from the following:

- Proximity to an event or value or idea – many teenagers may find it easier to get motivated regarding concerns that are real, material and immediate (while some older teenagers/young adults from more educated or more engaged backgrounds may relate to issues that are abstract or global). It is therefore easier to support youth democratic participation when both types of issues are addressed in political debates.
- Having decision-makers listen to and act on young people's concerns and opinions and from seeing the positive outcomes of these actions on local, social and individual contexts over a period of time. Again, the study finds that many young people feel insufficiently listened to by political elites.
- Motivation also comes from acting together with others and realising that one has efficacy to change local things.

The last point regarding the efficacy realised by 'acting together' again highlights the importance of building a 'Sense of Community', the Pilot partners have many activities planned that will support this type of community building for STEP, both online and offline. (see D5.1 section 4 for more in depth information as to what these activities are).

Table 3 shows the Pilot plans for the 2nd Phase of outreach strategies, including Target groups and key stakeholders and the environmental areas being targeted.

D4.1 : Youth Motivation Strategies

Indicative timeline: Months 17 to 19 (October – December 2016)	
Comune Di Sant' Agata del Bianco:	
Target groups - Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● cultural and social associations; ● secondary schools; ● youth organisations – youth councils; ● environmental organisations; ● local municipalities – association of municipalities of the Locride area.
Targeted areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● re-use, recycling and reduction of waste; ● water management; ● green spaces.
Mollet de Valles Municipality	
Target groups - Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cultural and sport associations ● Secondary schools ● Civic, cultural and sport public centres ● Consortium of Gallecs ● Regional authorities & associations
Targeted areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Local Action Plan for Young People (topics related to environment and sustainability) ● Municipal Action Plan (topics related to environment and sustainability) ● Food Policy at local level (ecological and environmentally friendly food, short circuits of distribution, etc) ● Urban and social gardens ● Environmental volunteering ● Nature itineraries (leisure and environmental education); ● air pollution ● green spaces – re-naturalisation/revitalisation of urban spaces ● sustainable use of environmental resources ● management of protected areas ● recycling ● energy efficiency -
Valdemoro Municipality	
Target groups - Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Environmental NGOs. (Espartal-Ecologistas en Acción, Animal protection, Aiba Association, etc.) ● Schools and High Schools/ Education centres ● youth associations and youth groups ● sports clubs
Targeted areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● creation of green spaces ● efficient use of environmental resources ● sustainable management of protected areas (Parque Regional del Sureste) ● green transportation (e.g. bicycles)

D4.1 : Youth Motivation Strategies

Region of Crete	
Target groups - Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊙ “Ecocrete” network (umbrella organisation) (www.ecocrete.gr) ⊙ Local sports clubs ⊙ Local cultural organisations ⊙ Informal groups (scouts, university student’s clubs, etc.)
Targeted areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊙ management of Natura 2000 areas ⊙ waste disposal ⊙ energy efficiency, climate change, environmental risks and causes for natural disasters ⊙ marine spatial planning & integrated coastal zone management
Hatay Metropolitan Municipality	
Target groups - Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊙ Environmental NGO’s & Companies ⊙ Chamber of Commerce ⊙ Farmers’ association ⊙ local municipalities (environment heads) ⊙ forest related business ⊙ hospitals & public agencies
Targeted areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊙ biodiversity (esp. medicine & aromatic plants) ⊙ urban ecology ⊙ water management ⊙ climate change

Table 3: Pilot Plans for Phase 2: Months 17-19 October-December 2016

Specific Activities have been planned by the Pilots to utilise the STEP platform in their participation processes, these can be viewed in much more detail in D5.1 section 4. Local Pilot Operation Plans they are not included in this Deliverable as they should be viewed in the context of the objectives for each of the Pilot regions. For each region the Pilot eParticipation Process is clearly defined and fully considers:

- ⊙ Objectives & Scope of the Participation Process
- ⊙ Legal Frameworks to be considered
- ⊙ Issues to be brought under public participation
- ⊙ Public Participation Procedures
- ⊙ Timeframes for the processes
- ⊙ Scenario Selection
- ⊙ Resources and Skills required (listing people responsible for specific tasks)
- ⊙ Communication to Stakeholders
- ⊙ Communication to Young Citizens
- ⊙ Social Media Management
- ⊙ Inclusion

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